

MobileAge

D5.2 First Communication and Dissemination Report

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List of abbreviations

<Abbreviation>	<Explanation>
AGE	AGE Platform Europe AISBL
AUTH	Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis
B2B	Business to Business
DoW	Description of Work
EC	European Commission
Gov2u	Government To You
FTB	Evangelische Stiftung Volmarstein
H2020	Horizon 2020 Programme
EIP AHA	European Innovation Partnership on Active and Healthy Ageing
EIP SCC	European Innovation Partnership on Smart Cities and Communities
Ifib	Institut Fur Informationsmanagement Bremen GMBH
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OSCPEP	Open Senior Citizen Public Service Engagement Platform
RCM	Region of Central Macedonia
TT	Tingtun AS
ULANC	Lancaster University
UPM	Universidad Politecnica De Madrid
ZGZ	Ayuntamiento De Zaragoza
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

Starting in February 2016 and running for 36 months, Mobile-Age is a H2020 EU co-funded project that targets a group of citizens that are usually marginalized as far as contemporary, technical innovations are concerned: seniors. Thus, Mobile-Age will focus on open government data, mobile technology and the provision of public services by developing methodological and technological innovations which address the difficulties older persons often face when using public services based on open government data.

Digital technologies including mobile technologies have expanded considerably across Europe over the last decade, however studies consistently show that older citizens use the internet and digital technologies less than the rest of the population. Likewise, while electronic access to government services and open data has expanded, not all user groups have made equal use of these services, and services that provide access to open data have not always been designed with the needs of older citizens in mind. As the use of public services based on open government data within Europe is increasing rapidly, it is crucial to ensure that no one is left behind.

The Mobile-Age project seeks to respond to these issues by developing and innovating processes of co-creation with older citizens by designing and developing mobile-based applications focused on older citizens' needs and expectations. Towards this aim, older citizens will work with researchers to help to ensure that the products developed are accessible, meet the needs and requirements of the older citizens involved, and thus provide relevant accessible services. The project will focus specifically on four use case scenarios for older citizens across Europe: social inclusion, independent living, a safe and accessible city for older people and access to health information, in collaboration with public authorities in Germany (Bremen), United Kingdom (South Lakeland), Spain (Zaragoza) and Greece (Region of Central Macedonia).

D5.2 (First Communication and Dissemination Report) aims to outline the dissemination and communication activities that were implemented during the first year of the project following the initial action plan of activities as described in deliverable D5.1 (Communication and Dissemination Plan), (M2).

The current deliverable includes the following chapters:

- Introduction – the introductory presents the Mobile-Age project in detail focusing on WP5 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation and the current deliverable “D5.2 First Communication and Dissemination Report”.
- Dissemination and communication objectives of the reporting period – a detailed description of WP5 efforts on developing and implementing the appropriate dissemination and communication strategy and activities that will result in the best and most effective promotion of the project at local, European and international level.
- Dissemination and communication tools and activities – an overview of the dissemination tools and activities created and performed by the Mobile-Age partners in order to raise visibility of the project during its first year of implementation.

- Dissemination activities for Y2 – an outline of the dissemination activities that will be performed during the second year (M13-M24) of project's implementation.
- Conclusions are included in the last part of the deliverable.

1 Introduction

This introductory sections aims to briefly present: the project; the WP5 on Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation; the deliverable, its structure, its methodology and objectives.

1.1 The project: Mobile-Age

Mobile-Age is a H2020 EU co-funded project which will complete its project cycle in 36 months. The project will be implemented by a consortium comprised of ten partners, namely: Lancaster University (ULANC), Tingtun AS (TT), AGE Platform Europe AISBL (AGE), Evangelische Stiftung Volmarstein (FTB), Government To You (Gov2u), Institut Fur Informationsmanagement Bremen GMBH (ifib), Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis (AUTH), Universidad Politecnica De Madrid (UPM), Ayuntamiento De Zaragoza (ZGZ) and Region of Central Macedonia (RCM).

The project will focus on open government data, mobile technology and the provision of public services for senior citizens across Europe. Aiming at an inclusive ageing society, the project will offer innovative ways for senior civic engagement with open government through personalized mobile-based technologies and services. A co-creation methodological approach will be followed so as to enable senior citizens to actively participate in designing and developing services that will increase their involvement in digital and open government services?

Thus, Mobile-Age will achieve the co-creation of such services by pursuing the following specific objectives:

- Explore and implement innovative ways to support senior citizens to access and use public services through personal mobile technologies and based on open government data.
- Develop and deploy co-creation approaches and methodologies to engage senior citizens effectively in order to realize the benefits of open government data and mobile technologies for the ageing population.
- Develop a situated, practice-based understanding of accessibility, mobility and usability of services for older persons. Based on this knowledge we will develop a best practice guide and toolkit for service and technology design together with senior citizens.
- Develop a framework for impact assessment and evaluation for co-creation approaches to open service development for the ageing population.

The project will be implemented at four pilot sites, which are complementary in terms of local/regional authority, urban/rural features, and the presence of experts/novices on e-government: South Lakeland (UK); Bremen (Germany); Region of Central Macedonia (Greece); and Zaragoza (Spain).

The four pilot sites will each work on a specific use case of relevance for seniors' citizens: social inclusion (Bremen), extending independent living (South Lakeland), a safe and accessible city for seniors (Zaragoza) and personal health information (Central Macedonia).

1.2 WP5 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

WP5 is a subset of the Mobile-Age project, led by Government to You (Gov2u) and in which all the partners (ULANC, TT, AGE, FTB, ifib, AUTH, UPM, ZGZ and RCM) participate. The

successful implementation of WP5 objectives and tasks is highly dependent on the coherent, effective and fruitful collaboration of WP5 partners as well as on their individual active roles.

As clearly stated in the DoW, this work package aims to:

- Ensure that the Mobile-Age project will achieve the widest impact and most effective exploitation of the project results through:
 - An effective internal and external communications strategy while coordinating and assisting other work packages to meet their objectives regarding dissemination and communication.
 - Raising visibility and awareness of the project's objectives, developments and expected results.
 - Stakeholders' engagement, motivation and interaction.
 - Promote the project's exploitable results to all potential users and interested stakeholders at local, national and European level after the project's completion.

In this context, WP5 has designed, and is in charge of implementing, the overall dissemination and communication strategy, while it is also responsible for coordinating and report on dissemination activities undertaken to promote the project and its platform. WP5 will work towards the establishment of a wide network with audiences who have a vested interest in the project so as to raise awareness and visibility of Mobile-Age, and its services, encouraging senior citizens – mainly – to test these services throughout the platform's function.

The implementation of WP5 structures around the following tasks:

- Task 5.1 – Planning and Coordination of Communication and Dissemination Activities (Leader: Gov2u, duration: M1-M36)
- Task 5.2 – Implementation of Communication and Dissemination Activities (Leader: Gov2u, duration: M1-M36)
- Task 5.3 – Transferability, Sustainability and Business Plan (Leader: ifib, duration: M17-M34)
- Task 5.4 – Uptake of Mobile Solutions and Demonstrator Application by City Information Providers and Public Authorities (Leader: UPM, duration: M33-M36)

Moreover, a number of deliverables are related to this work package and they are presented in detail in section 1.4 of this deliverable.

1.3 The deliverable: D5.2 First Communication and Dissemination Report

1.3.1 Scope of the deliverable

The scope of this deliverable is to present a yearly report related to the dissemination and communication activities of the project performed by project partners. It outlines the dissemination and communication objectives and strategy of the reporting period and presents the tools and activities that were undertaken to accomplish the set objectives. Moreover, the deliverable reports on dissemination tools that were used within Y1 in order to disseminate the project and implement the strategy as it was set in the deliverable D5.1 (Communication and Dissemination Plan).

1.3.2 Methodology of the deliverable

The deliverable has been created based on the detailed description of WP5 objectives and tasks in the DoW and the close collaboration of WP5 leader with the project coordinator and the partners. Gov2u as the WP5 leader is responsible for the content of the deliverable which was produced and shared with partners for review, feedback and contributions in certain sections. The final version of the document was submitted to the project officer for final approval.

1.3.3 Structure of the deliverable

The first section provides an introduction to the project, WP5 and the deliverable. The second section describes the objectives and the strategy that was followed during Y1. The third section focuses on the dissemination and communication tools that were used, as well as activities that were implemented for the achievement of the objectives for the aforementioned period. Lastly, the fourth section outlines the activities that will be performed in the upcoming period M13-M24. At the end of this deliverable, conclusions highlight the main points that were presented in the current report.

Thus, the document is structured as follows:

- Introduction
- Dissemination and communication objectives for the reporting period
- Dissemination and communication tools and activities
- Dissemination Activities for Year 2
- Conclusions

1.3.4 Intended audience of the deliverable

The following table defines the intended audience of the current deliverable:

<i>Intended audience</i>	<i>Reasons for interest in reading</i>
Mobile-Age Consortium partners	To be informed on the communication and dissemination activities performed by the consortium during the reporting period (Feb.2016 – Jan. 2017).
European Commission	To review and assess this deliverable as a required report based on DoW of Mobile-Age.
Identified stakeholders	To be informed about the communication and dissemination activities performed within the reporting period, raise awareness about the project, announce project objectives as well as to find out how they could benefit from the services offered by Mobile-Age.
Partners participating in similar projects	To share knowledge, information, best practices and activities that could be utilized in their projects as well as to find common ground on which they could establish a potential collaboration of cross-dissemination with Mobile-Age.

Table 1 : Intended audience of the deliverable

1.4 Relation with other WP5 deliverables

D5.2 First Communication and Dissemination Report relates to the following deliverables:

- **D5.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan (M2):** this is the communication and dissemination strategy and actions that will be implemented throughout the project's lifetime in order to achieve the project's widest promotion, greatest visibility and awareness to the external audience. Moreover, this deliverable states clearly the methods and tools of internal communication within the work package.
- **D5.4 Update of the Communication and Dissemination Plan (M24):** this is the update of D5.1 deliverable and will include the updated action plan for Y3 of the project. Moreover, the dissemination strategy will be enhanced given the developments that will be performed up to M24 of the project, taking into account the objectives that will be set for Y3.
- **D5.6 Final Communication and Dissemination Report (M36):** this is the final report on communication and dissemination activities that partners will undertake during the last year of the project.

1.5 Quality of the deliverable

The initial table of content of the current deliverable was presented to project partners in November 2016 at the 3rd project meeting in Bremen. A draft of the deliverable was prepared by Gov2u and additions made by AGE, after which it was sent to the project coordinator for review and final submission to the EC. The deliverable is written in English, is included in the correct template of the project and a language quality control has been performed.

2 Dissemination and Communication objectives of the reporting period

This section presents in detail the dissemination and communication objectives and strategy implemented for the reporting period (M1-M12).

During the reporting period, WP5 focused its efforts on developing and implementing the appropriate dissemination and communication strategy and activities that will result in the best and most effective promotion of the project at local, European and international level.

Additionally, an internal communication strategy was developed by defining roles (WP5 main contact points and press focal points) and responsibilities, thus ensuring that each partner promotes the project, and that all partners contribute equally to the implementation of the project objectives.

For the first year of project's implementation, the main objectives of WP5 were the following:

- Design and launch the Mobile-Age website;
- Design and create the promotional material of the project (logo, overall presentation, newsletter, press release, project brochure, project factsheet, poster, social media)
- Monitor the project's website and social media profiles.
- Identify and organize the stakeholders groups;
- Participation in events at national and European level to raise awareness and visibility for the project;
- Coordinate with partners for their better engagement at local level and stronger involvement;
- Establish, maintain and enhance collaboration with other similar EU funded projects;
- Promote the project to the press and media at local, national and European level;
- Provide deliverables and reports corresponding to the reporting period M1-M12.

3 Dissemination and Communication tools and activities

An overview of the dissemination tools and activities created and performed by the Mobile-Age partners in order to raise visibility of the project during its first year of implementation (M1-M12) is provided in this chapter.

Dissemination tools are the communication channels where messages from the project are conveyed to stakeholders and to the general public.

3.1 Dissemination and Communication tools

This section presents the dissemination and communication tools used during the reporting period. These tools are the means through which the project's main messages can be transmitted and communicated outside the consortium. A common branding was, and will continue to be used, throughout promotional materials with the intention of maintaining a consistent and distinctive identity in order to evoke a positive image and a favorable reputation for the project.

3.1.1 Mobile-Age Website

The website was created in M4 (May 2016) of the project and is the most informative and resourceful dissemination tool. It consists a major channel of information and communication for visitors and, for this reason, is harmonized and interrelated with the main goals of WP5 to disseminate the project findings as well as to engage key stakeholders with a view to knowledge sharing.

The website is a means to convey all information pertained to the project for a range of audiences. Since its launch, the website is regularly updated to maintain a sustained interest in project activities. Updates highlight project news, project in the press, events, relevant articles, press releases, newsletter issues, synergies and other activities dedicated to dissemination. The update of the website content, layout and design is ongoing throughout the implementation of the project.

Data retrieved from the back end of the Mobile-Age website is presented in the table below:

<i>Field</i>	<i>Data</i>
Newsletter subscribers	94
Number of items on News	47
Number of items on Events	33

Table 2 : Project website data

Data retrieved on 13th January 2017 from Google Analytics on the Mobile-Age website are presented in the following table:

<i>Field</i>	<i>Data</i>
Users (unique visitors)	1,912
Number of Sessions (visits)	3,036

Number of Page views	8,620
Average Session Duration	03min 16sec
Number of New Visits	1,911
Number of Returning Visits	1,125
New visits vs Returning visits (percentage)	62.9% - 37.1%

Table 3 : Website data from Google Analytics (May 2016 – January 2017)

3.1.2 Mailing Lists

A data base of contacts including stakeholders and interested parties from local regional, national and European level has been created by WP5 leader, Gov2u, and project partners continue to contribute to this activity.

This data base has been used to make announcements related to the project about specific achievements, developments, event participation, etc. The aim of using these lists is to raise awareness about Mobile-Age, and to inform and engage stakeholders.

These lists will be updated throughout the project’s duration.

3.1.3 Mobile-Age Social Media

Social media profiles play a promotional role for the project and promote visibility of the project to a wide range of audiences. Their popularity, ease of access and rapid information flow identify them as very effective online dissemination tools, therefore profiles in Facebook and Twitter were created before the website launch. A LinkedIn group was created later on (M5) in order to support the project’s dissemination activities and to acquire presence in this social network

Regular posts and updates relating to the project’s developments and news, as well as reporting interesting news from the web related to the project’s topic have been publicised during the reporting period.

The following tables present the number of “likes”, “followers” and “members” so far, the month that they were created together with their links:

<i>Field</i>	<i>Details</i>
Social Network	Facebook
Project Month	M2
URL	www.facebook.com/mobileageeu
Status	62 likes

Table 4 : Mobile-Age page on Facebook

<i>Field</i>	<i>Details</i>
--------------	----------------

Social Network	Twitter
Project Month	M1
URL	twitter.com/MobileAgeEU
Status	165 followers, 204 tweets

Table 5 : Mobile-Age profile on Twitter

Field	Details
Social Network	LinkedIn
Project Month	M5
URL	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/8475752
Status	35 members

Table 6 : Mobile-Age group on LinkedIn

3.1.3.1 Facebook Page Insights & Hootsuite Twitter profile summary

“Facebook Page Insights” is a free service for all Facebook Pages and Facebook Platform application and websites. Facebook Insights provides Facebook Page owners and Facebook Platform developers with metrics about their content. By understanding and analyzing trends within user growth and demographics, consumption of content, and creation of content, Page owners and Platform developers are better equipped to improve their business with Facebook. Only Page administrators, application owners, and domain administrators can view Insights data for the properties they own or administer. The metrics data is aggregated on a daily basis and is made available within 24 hours after a full day is complete.

The figures presented in Appendix III show overall data from Facebook Page Insights for the Mobile-Age page within the reporting period. In the Appendix III, data on “Number of people the posts reached”, “Total Page Likes”, as well as the post that most people reached within the reporting period, etc. are presented.

The profile summary of Mobile-Age Twitter profile is provided by the free version of the Hootsuite tool. This tool is a Social Media Management System that helps its users to keep track of, and manage, their social network channels. Multiple networks such as Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and Google+ can be managed at the same time using this tool. Moreover it provides Analytic tools for users’ profiles. The profile summary and followers growth can be found in Appendix IV.

3.1.4 Newsletter

As described in the DoW, the Mobile-Age quarterly e-newsletter will be the main tool to disseminate updated information on the project work in progress.

- The 1st Newsletter Issue was launched in June 2016 announcing the project’s objectives, promotional materials created, the launch of the first press release, Mobile-Age events and workshops organized by partners in the pilot sites, other news, upcoming events and conferences and interesting publications.

- The 2nd Newsletter Issue was released in October 2016 announcing the project’s developments, Mobile-Age events and workshops organized by partners in the pilot sites, other news, upcoming events and conferences and interesting publications.

The structure of the newsletter is outlined in Appendix V.

<i>Issue</i>	<i>Date of release</i>	<i>Available in URL</i>
Newsletter Issue No.1	June 2016	http://www.mobile-age.eu/newsletters-issues/newsletter-issue-no-1-%E2%80%93-june-2016.html
Newsletter Issue No.2	October 2016	http://www.mobile-age.eu/newsletters-issues/newsletter-issue-no-2-october-2016.html
Newsletter Issue No.3	January 2017	Link not available at time of report submission

Table 7 : Newsletter Issues

Newsletters have been circulated by email to all subscribers as well as to other target groups and similar initiatives that have been incorporated into the mailing list by the dissemination and communication team.

Both issues have been approved and posted on Joinup Platform.

- **1st Issue:** <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/news/mobile-age-project-co-created-personalised-mobile-access-public-services-senior-citizens-1st-ne>
- **2nd Issue:** <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/news/mobile-age-project-co-created-personalised-mobile-access-public-services-senior-citizens-%E2%80%93-2nd->

Moreover, they are accessible via the Mobile-Age website under the section “Project Outcomes”, subsection “Newsletter Issues”. Website visitors can easily subscribe to the newsletter distribution list and follow the project’s progress.

The fourth issue of the newsletter will be released in April 2017.

3.1.5 Press Release

Apart from the project website, press releases are considered the second most efficient tool for the dissemination of the project since their distribution to a large number of recipients (media outlets, similar organizations, similar initiatives and projects, academia, communities and networks, etc.) help promote the project at national and pan-European level. Press releases will be produced throughout the project’s lifetime. Its purpose is the media engagement in the dissemination of the project’s achievements and milestones.

Gov2u, as the dissemination and communication leader, is responsible for the creation of press releases. Once created, they are shared with the press focal points nominated by each partner. The press focal points are responsible for the translation of the press releases in to the partners’ native language (if necessary), and for the distribution of the articles to media outlets at national level. Therefore, press focal points enhance Gov2u’s efforts and further awareness and visibility of the project is achieved.

“Media Guidelines for press focal points” were created by Gov2u on the purpose of explaining the procedure for press focal points to follow to achieve correct dissemination and wider promotion of the press releases.

The first [Mobile-Age Press release](#) for announcing the project’s launch was published in May 2016 and can be found in electronic version at project’s website in section “Project Outcomes”, subsection “Press releases”.

3.1.6 Promotional Material

Gov2u has created a series of dissemination materials in order to create and maintain the common identity of the project, raise its visibility and support project partners to their promotional activities in workshops, face to face meetings, etc.

The following project promotional materials were created during Y1 and were uploaded to the project’s website:

- [Factsheet](#)
- [Academic Poster](#)
- [Brochure](#)
- [Poster](#)
- [Poster short version](#)
- [Project Overall Presentation](#)

In Appendix VI, the reader can find an overview of the dissemination materials created by Gov2u.

The layout of all promotional material include the Mobile-Age logo, the project’s grant agreement number and the EU emblem.

3.2 Dissemination and Communication activities

The following sections outline the dissemination activities that have been carried out during the reporting period. The input to this section is based to the Dissemination Activities Report template that was internally circulated to partners for completion regarding their activities corresponding to each section.

3.2.1 Organization of events

<i>Partner’s Name</i>	<i>Name of the event</i>	<i>Date of the event</i>	<i>Location of the event (city, country)</i>	<i>Description of the event (type, aim, size of the audience, type of the audience)</i>
ULANC	Kick off meeting	9th – 10th of February 2016	Lancaster, UK	First meeting of all Mobile-Age partners
ULANC	Policy & networking meeting	18th -19th of February 2016	Brussels, Belgium	Meeting with project officer and other project partners funded under H2020 INSO-ICT – enabled open government
ifib	Meeting with intermediaries	3rd of March	Bremen Osterholz,	Meeting with local computer group in order

	and/or potential participants	2016	Germany	to collaborate as well as to recruit and engage senior citizens.
ifib	First information event about Mobile-Age	23rd of May 2016	Bremen Osterholz, Germany	Senior citizens from the district were invited to jointly design and develop a mobile application for their district together with the ifib project team. Participants: 13 senior citizens and 2 intermediaries
ifib	Kick-off workshop	8th of June 2016	Bremen Osterholz, Germany	Presenting the project, get to know each other and give out cultural probes. Participants: 11 senior citizens and 2 intermediaries
ifib	Mobile-Age Focus Group	20th of June 2016	Bremen Osterholz, Germany	Organized a focus group regarding interesting places for the senior citizens in the district of Osterholz (where to go when going for a walk, for shopping, for meeting people etc.).
ULANC	Workshop 1	21st of June 2016	South Lakeland, UK	Five participants shared their biggest concerns about 'using' mobile technology, computers and the internet and were encouraged to discuss their concerns and fears in depth and to ask researchers for help using their mobile phones/I-pads directly. This exercise enabled senior citizens to ask questions about the techniques of using certain features of, for example, a mobile phone, and presented an opportunity for researchers to advise on technology use and to gain an understanding the

				underlying issues relating to technology use among senior citizens that are important to keep in mind for designing the 'Mobile-Age' App in the next phase of the project.
ULANC	Workshop 2	24th of June 2016	South Lakeland, UK	<p>Following a brief introduction for new attendees and a general discussion around problems, benefits and using technology among the senior citizens, researchers conducted a 'calendar' exercise with the participants which allowed the senior citizens to explore the theme of their 'ideal week' by comparing their actual week of activities from Monday to Sunday with their ideal week. The purpose of this exercise was to understand what activities people filled their days with to keep active, do necessary chores and avoid feeling lonely, as well as gaining an understanding of the role of technology in supporting and improving the quality of daily life. Participants: 8</p>
ULANC	Workshop 3	30th of June 2016	South Lakeland, UK	<p>This workshop was intended as a feedback session from the calendar exercise, however as only two participants were able to attend, the event unfolded as one of discussion around challenges of seniors knowing what relevant information is available to them online and how to access this information, in</p>

				addition to how researchers could facilitate this access for senior citizens. Participants: 2
ULANC/ZGZ	Management Board Meeting 2	4th-5th of July 2016	Zaragoza, Spain	Second meeting of all Mobile-Age partners
ifib	Cultural probes workshop	12th of July 2016	Bremen Osterholz, Germany	Joint reflection on activity and experience with cultural probes. Defining some key characteristics for the personas. Participants: 9 senior citizens
ULANC	Workshop 4	12th of July 2016	South Lakeland, UK	Researchers fed back the results of the calendar exercise to attendees, offering insights into the eight dominant themes that had emerged both from this exercise and previous interviews. The intention of this event was to order the themes according to relevance for each participant. Due to time constraints, not all themes were covered, however the participants struggled to prioritise the themes and left the event feeling enthused to return in September to participate in our design-oriented workshops. By this stage the participants and researchers had developed good personal relationships, sharing things about their lives with each other. Participants: 4
ifib	Personas workshop	16th of August 2016	Bremen Osterholz, Germany	Joint examination of communication- and information needs as well as resources of the senior

				citizens in OSTERHOLZ through working with personas. 8 participants, 1 intermediary
ULANC	Meeting with SLDC and Age UK South Lakeland staff	25th of August 2016	South Lakeland, UK	The purpose of this meeting was to enable researchers to report on results of fieldwork to date and for the intermediaries to offer feedback and advice, after which discussions around themes of possible intervention emerged.
ifib	Workshop on informational content	7th of September 2016	Bremen Osterholz, Germany	Data definition: Working out the relevant attributes for the objects of the application. Participants: 12 senior citizens
FTB	Co-creation workshop with seniors	7th of September 2016	Bremen, Germany	Introduction to project work; planning of activities
ifib	Focus group with members of men's breakfast club	10th of September 2016	Bremen Osterholz, Germany	Supplement of the data collection with a distinct group of seniors and to recruit some of them for further co-creation. Participants: 6 senior citizens
FTB	Ceremonial Act and Conference "25 years FTB – Technology for Inclusion and Participation	12th of September 2016	parliament building of North-Rhine-Westfalia, Düsseldorf, Germany	Ceremony, conference, exhibition; 300 participants: politicians, ministries, AT users, user organisations, technology partners, companies
ULANC	Workshop	13th of September 2016	South Lakeland, UK	The theme of 'events' that senior citizens like to attend was explored. Following a brainstorming session on issues such as nature of event, information gathering on event, transport to get to event, participants carried out an exercise which

				involved searching for information on various aspects of events and the accessibility of (open) data tied to the events. A lively discussion generated further insights into senior's needs, preferences, difficulties, frustrations and design ideas.
ULANC	Workshop	27th of September 2016	South Lakeland, UK	Seniors carried out a set of exercises based on insights gathered at the previous workshop. They explored specific websites on their own mobile devices (including laptops) for example, property sale websites. Researchers observed their interaction with mobile devices, offering assistance where necessary and exploring difficulties faced when navigating the web sites. Participants commented on what they would find helpful/ideal support in situations involving website surfing. The workshop was fruitful in understanding App design features that the participants would appreciate, and that could be developed and installed, on their mobile devices in order to facilitate web surfing. It was also suggestive of additional data/features that may be useful to incorporate in future versions of the App prototype.
ifib	Workshop on applications	29th of September	Bremen Osterholz,	Work on the interactive elements of the application. Participants: 7

		2016	Germany	senior citizens, 1 intermediary
FTB	Co-creation workshop with seniors	29th of September 2016	Bremen, Germany	Potential applications
ifib	Focus group on data co-creation	1st & 26th of October 2016	Bremen Osterholz, Germany	Data co-creation on nice places and walks and on meeting points, advice and cultural offerings at "Mens breakfast". Participants: 3 senior citizens
ifib	Workshop on map design	13th of October 2016	Bremen Osterholz, Germany	Specification and agreement on a map display. Participants: 10 senior citizens
FTB	Co-creation workshop with seniors	13th of October 2016	Bremen, Germany	Map presentations of Google, OSM, Bing and FTB's ideas, search in databases
AGE	AGE Task force on Healthy ageing and accessibility	24th of October 2016	Brussels, Belgium	Meeting of the Task forces of AGE, with 12 participants (older people's representatives and experts in the field). Presentation of the project via leaflets
ifib	Design- and data workshop	27th of October 2016	Bremen Osterholz, Germany	Collection, discussion and completion of senior citizens' data collection & decisions on filter and landmarks. Participants 9 senior citizens, 2 stakeholders, 1 intermediary
ifib	Meeting with local internet group BORIS	27th of October 2016	Bremen Osterholz, Germany	Meeting with local group: Engagement in data co creation on nice places and walks. Participants: 3 senior citizens
FTB	Co-creation workshop with seniors	27th of October 2016	Bremen, Germany	Creation of „deficiency reporter“ and „nice places“

ifib	Meeting with senior citizen for data co-creation	3rd of November 2016	Bremen Osterholz, Germany	Information collection and editing, co creation of data on nice places and walks. Participant: 1 senior citizens
ifib	Workshop on interface design	8th of November 2016	Bremen Osterholz, Germany	Paper mock-ups on interfaces. Participants: 6 senior citizens
FTB	Co-creation workshop with seniors	8th of November 2016	Bremen, Germany	Co-creation of paper mockups, development of scenarios
ifib	Workshop on 1 st page	17th of November 2016	Bremen Osterholz, Germany	Discussion of content and design of the start page for the mobile website. Participants: 8 senior citizens
FTB	Co-creation workshop with seniors	17th of November 2016	Bremen, Germany	Paper mockups, comment function, picture-upload
ULANC/ifib	Management Board meeting 3	22nd -23rd of November 2016	Bremen, Germany	Third meeting of all Mobile-Age partners
ifib	Tablet workshop	29th of November 2016	Bremen Osterholz, Germany	Tablet introduction and passing out the tablets, demonstration of the prototype. Participants: 9 senior citizens
FTB	co-creation workshop with seniors	29th of November 2016	Bremen, Germany	Distribution of tablet PCs, introduction to demo app
ifib	Workshop on 1st page	8th of December 2016	Bremen Osterholz, Germany	Talking about experiences with tablets and prototype. Demonstration and discussion of first version of the start page design and work on the content for the start page. Participants: 8 senior citizens
FTB	Co-creation workshop with	8th of December 2016	Bremen, Germany	Presentation of new start page of app, report on personal experiences with

	seniors			app
FTB	Co-creation workshop with seniors	15th of December 2016	Bremen, Germany	Discussion of personal experiences with app

Table 8 : Organization of events

3.2.2 Participation in conferences, workshops and events

<i>Partner's Name</i>	<i>Name of the event</i>	<i>Date of the event</i>	<i>Location of the event (city, country)</i>	<i>Description of the event (type, aim, size of the audience, type of the audience)</i>
AGE	Towards a new dynamic eGovernment Action Plan 2016-2020	4th of March 2016	Brussels, Belgium	<p>On 4 March 2016, DG Connect organised the event 'Towards a new dynamic eGovernment Action Plan 2016-2020' that took place at the Crowne Plaza in Brussels, bringing together 120 interested parties from civil society, businesses/Industry, associations/Institutions and Public Administrations.</p> <p>During the first part of the day the two following studies were presented by the DG CNECT H3 Public Services and an external study team:</p> <p>Towards faster take up of new eGovernment services</p> <p>The value of new eGovernment Services</p> <p>This was followed by a presentation of the main outcomes of the Public Consultation on the new eGovernment Action Plan that was held between 30 October 2015 and 22 January 2016.</p> <p>The second part of the day evolved around a panel discussion between various stakeholders who elaborated on their expectations of the new eGovernment Action Plan followed by a discussion with the participants</p>
AGE	Inclusive Smart Cities. Co-design and co-	18th of March 2016	Webinar	Citizen focus is a Key Horizontal Enabler Action Cluster in the Smart Cities Strategic Implementation Plan

	creation as tools for citizen engagement			(SIP). It is linked to the other 5 Action Clusters. https://eu-smartcities.eu/content/citizen-city About 35 various stakeholders, mainly public authorities and urban planner, joined the webinar.
AGE	EESC Hearing 125 million seniors in the EU: a boost for numerical growth?	30th of March 2016	Brussels, Belgium	Hearing at the European Economic and Social Committee http://www.eesc.europa.eu/?i=portal.en.events-and-activities-125-million-senior-citizens
ifib	Partec completion workshop	26th – 27th of April 2016	Bremen, Germany	Completion workshop of the project Partec, presenting the results of researching participatory technology development with older people
AGE	TechSoup - Technology for Social Good	13th of June 2016	Brussels, Belgium	About 50 stakeholders, especially researchers and designers of technological apps http://www.techsoupeurope.org/
AGE	DSI4EU: Shaping the Future of Digital Social Innovation in Europe	29th of June 2016	Brussels, Belgium	This policy workshop on Digital Social Innovation for Europe brought together innovators throughout Europe and leaders from CAPS projects with European Commission Policy officials to get in touch, get inspired and to network. Attendees where CAPS project partners and EC policy representatives (about 50 people)
AGE	ACCESS European Conference	30th of August 2016	Brussels, Belgium	Presentation of the ACCESS App for older people's quality of life ; AGE presented Mobile-Age to an audience of about 40 people, mainly service providers in the field of care and cure in Belgium.
ifib	EASST conference http://www.sts2016bcn.org/	31st of August – 3rd of September 2016	Barcelona, Spain	Joint Conference of the European Association for the Study of Science and Technology (EASST) and Society for Social Studies of Science (4S)

AGE	"Towards early detection of age-related health risks: understanding users' needs, unobtrusive sensing and data analysis"	4th of October 2016	Brussels, Belgium	During the workshop, all PHC-21 projects (i-PROGNOSIS, FrailSafe, PreventIT, REACH, my-AHA, City4Age) were presented and open discussion took place regarding future challenges in collecting, storing, using, sharing and analysing data for Active and Healthy Ageing from an interdisciplinary perspective. About 50 participants, especially researchers and project partners.
Ayuntami ento Zaragoza	Madrid Open Cities Summit 2016	5th of October 2016	Madrid, Spain	http://opencitiessummit.org/
Ayuntami ento Zaragoza	IODC16	6th of October 2016	Madrid, Spain	http://opendatacon.org/
ifib	INSIST Conference	7th – 8th of October 2016	Munich, Germany	Junior conference of the Interdisciplinary Network for Studies Investigating Science and Technology
AGE	EU Open Days side event on Smart cities and communities for all: How to become smart and age-friendly	10th of October 2016	Brussels, Belgium	The event was attended by ca 70 people from local authorities, EU institutions, civil society organisations, researchers, etc. Mobile-Age leaflets were displayed.
AGE	DOREMI final conference	25th of October 2016	Brussels, Belgium	Final conference of the project, attended by about 15 seniors, 20 researchers, 5 policy makers' representatives and 5 business representatives http://www.age-platform.eu/policy-work/news/doremi-project-final-conference
ifib	Seminar: Becoming old in the age of mediatization	31st of October – 1st of November	Copenhagen, Denmark	Research seminar on becoming old in the age of mediatization

		2016		
AGE	AGE General Assembly and Annual Conference	17th – 18th of November 2016	Brussels, Belgium	The events were attended by 110 representatives of older people's associations from all over the EU on day 1, and from 140 participants on day 2 (110 older people's representatives + 30 external participants, especially policy representatives).
ifib	4th Annual Conference AGE Platform	18th of November 2016	Brussels, Belgium	AGE member-organisations, policy-makers and external guests discuss how the EU should address age discrimination, while strengthening both economic and social rights of older people in order to empower them as equal citizens.
AGE	Inclusive Smart Cities: A European Manifesto on Citizen Engagement	23rd of November 2016	Brussels, Belgium	AGE Secretary General was speaking at the event and mentioned Mobile-Age activities and first WP1 results. The event was attended by ca. 50/60 people.
AGE	EU Summit on Innovation for active and healthy ageing	6th -7th of December 2016	Brussels, Belgium	Mobile-Age's leaflets and a PowerPoint slide on Mobile-Age were displayed in the exhibition area, visited by ca 1000 people.
ifib	2nd transdisciplinary conference: „Technische Unterstützungssysteme, die die Menschen wirklich wollen“	12th – 13th of December 2016	Hamburg, Germany	Researchers and industry representatives from different disciplines present their research in presentations, posters and demonstrations
TT	Language technologies for Europe EC Round Table	13th of December 2016	Luxembourg, Luxembourg	Consultation workshop on future R&I priorities in language technologies Audience about 30. Participants from Companies using or producing Language technologies (e.g. Facebook, Booking.com etc.)

Table 9 : Participation in conferences, workshops and events

3.2.3 Direct contact with stakeholders (face-to-face meetings)

<i>Partner's Name</i>	<i>Name and type of the contact</i>	<i>Date of the meeting</i>	<i>Venue/Location of the meeting</i>	<i>Activity description (short description of the outcome of the meeting, what we gained from it)</i>
FTB	Meeting with Bremen-online	1st of March 2016	Bremen, University	Discussion on open data from Bremen, cooperation
FTB	Meeting with Bremen-online	14th of March 2016	Bremen, University	Discussion on open data from Bremen, rights, interfaces, accessibility
AGE	Meeting with Eurocities members	23rd of June 2016	Brussels, Belgium	Presentation of Mobile-Age, liaison with 3 members of EUROCITIES and 3 policy officer (awareness raising meeting)
AGE	Meeting with EIP SCC Citizens Focus Action Cluster leads	27th of June 2016	Skype meeting	Presentation of Mobile-Age to Mario Conci, lead of the EIP SCC Citizens Focus Action Cluster leads and John Zib, responsible for the co-creation working group
FTB	Meeting with managers from Bethel foundation	11th of July 2016	FTB, Wetter, Germany	Information on project
RCM (Stampoulis, Karagiannis, Syritsidou)	Medical Association of Thessaloniki (various Employees including one from technical department)	18th of October 2016	4, Aristotelous Square, Medical Association Offices	Organising the process of retrieving the dataset of doctors records to our database. We also got a first export of the dataset in order to get familiar with it.
ULANC-South Lakes Housing	Meeting	19th of October 2016	Kendal, UK	Researchers met with the South Lakes Housing sheltered housing manager and senior scheme manager with a

				view to boosting recruitment of seniors in phase 2 of the project.
FTB	Meeting with Bremen-online	27th of October 2016	Bremen, University	Discussion on open data from Bremen, details on data access
ULANC	Invited talk	Arranged for 2nd of February 2017	CeMoRe Showcase event, Lancaster University	Mobile-Age: Addressing loneliness and social isolation amongst older adults (Niall Hayes)
ULANC	Submitted Conference paper	Arranged for 6th – 11th May 2017	Colorado Convention Centre, Denver, CO	Mobile-Age: Open data apps to support independent living
ULANC	Submitted Conference paper	Arranged for 10th - 17th June 2017	Designing Interactive Systems 2017, Edinburgh	Reflecting on the „co“ in co-creation

Table 10 : Direct contact with stakeholders

3.2.4 Communication with stakeholders (via email, social media, phone, contact form of the website, etc.)

<i>Partner's Name</i>	<i>Name and type of the contact</i>	<i>Date of the meeting</i>	<i>Venue/Location of the meeting</i>	<i>Activity description (short description of the outcome of the meeting, what we gained from it)</i>
FTB	Phone and email with Rhein-Neckar-Verkehr GmbH, Referat Digitalisierung	9th of June 2016	RNV has interest in providing open data on public transport	Contact again in the last phase of the project
RCM	Pharmacist (Stamatia Zoidou)	17th of October 2016 (phone)	Clarification of prescription process	Details of the process of doctors prescribing medicine to patients (e.g. they mostly prescribe a drastic substance but sometimes they specify medicine with its name)

Table 11 : Communication with stakeholders**3.2.5 Media coverage**

Media coverage of Mobile-Age has high importance as target groups can be reached at local and pan European level. This practice also helps to increase project impact and informs stakeholders about the project's developments and achievements. A detailed table of these activities can be found in Appendix I.

3.2.6 Liaison with other projects, networks & initiatives

During the reporting period Gov2u has conducted online research about similar projects that belong in the same thematic area as Mobile-Age and has made contact with them.

An invitation was sent to 33 similar EU funded projects, 12 of whom responded positively to create synergies and promote cross-dissemination of the project. Lastly, 7 out of 12 similar projects have provided their description and logo which are displayed on the Mobile-Age website in the section 'Useful Links', subsection 'Similar Projects'. This list will be regularly updated and Gov2U will continue to contact these projects to provide further dissemination activities. A list of projects that were approached can be found in Appendix VII.

The following table presents the similar EU funded projects that accepted Mobile-Age's invitation for synergy creation and cross-dissemination.

<i>Project</i>	<i>Action</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Website</i>
FrailSafe project	Horizon 2020 funded project	Ageing, clinical status of frailty	http://www.frailsafe-project.eu
ECOMODE project	Horizon 2020 funded project	Touch-less mobile devices usable also by older adults and visually impaired people for handling every day issues using ICT	http://www.ecomode-project.eu/index.php
3D Tune-In	Horizon 2020 funded project	Digital games in the field of hearing aid technologies and hearing loss in children and older adults, addressing social inclusion, generating new markets and creating job opportunities	http://3d-tune-in.eu/
iCareCoops	AAL Joint Programme (ACTIVE AND ASSISTED LIVING PROGRAMME)	Promoting and supporting elderly care cooperatives as a model to organise elderly care in an efficient way.	http://project.icarecoops.eu/
SENIOR-TV	AAL Joint Programme (ACTIVE AND ASSISTED LIVING PROGRAMME)	A platform for providing formal and informal caregiving services to older adults that live alone in their own homes, at low cost, and that focuses on the active	http://www.aal-europe.eu/projects/senior-tv/ , http://seniortv-aal.eu/

		prevention and the maintenance of relationships with friends, family, and the community	
SmartBEAT	AAL Joint Programme (ACTIVE AND ASSISTED LIVING PROGRAMME)	Supporting senior Heart Failure patients, their family, relatives and friends, cardiologists and general healthcare professionals accessing innovative ICT solutions that promote an easier, wider and sustainable access to healthcare	http://www.smartbeatproject.org/
ELF@Home	AAL Joint Programme (ACTIVE AND ASSISTED LIVING PROGRAMME)	A self-care solution based on self-check of health conditions and fitness at home. The solution will use an autonomous fitness system targeting not frailty or pre-frailty elder people aged over 65 years and living independently at home.	http://elfathome.eu/
IN LIFE - INdependent Living support Functions for the Elderly	Horizon 2020 funded project	Offers all-around, personalised, multi-faceted existing ICT solutions and services addressing diverse daily activities (eating, physical activity, commuting, mental stimulation, communication, social interaction, etc.) to users with cognitive impairment living in their own home or in sheltered homes, as well as to their formal and informal carers. Emphasis is placed on elderly and carer interactions, communications and care scheduling and monitoring.	http://www.inlife-project.eu/
ENRICHME: ENabling Robot and assisted living environment for Independent Care and Health Monitoring of the Elderly	Horizon 2020 funded project	Enriching the day-to-day experiences of elderly people at home by means of technologies that enable health monitoring, complementary care and social support, helping them to remain active and independent for longer and to enhance their quality of life.	http://www.enrichme.eu/wordpress/

PreventIT	Horizon 2020 funded project	Develops mobile technology that enables early identification of risk factors for functional decline in younger older adults, and empowers them to self-manage their own health and function by adopting a healthy, active lifestyle.	http://www.preventit.eu/
Prosperity4All	FP7 funded project	Develops the infrastructure to allow a new ecosystem to grow; one that is based on self-rewarding collaboration, that can reduce redundant development, lower costs, increase market reach and penetration internationally, and create the robust cross-platform spectrum of mainstream and assistive technology based access solutions required.	http://www.prosperity4all.eu/
ROUTE-TO-PA	Horizon 2020 funded project	Aims at improving the engagement of citizens by making them able to socially interact over open data, by forming or joining existing online communities that share common interest and discuss common issues.	http://routetopa.eu/

Table 12 : Created synergies with similar EU funded projects

3.2.6.1 Joinup

Joinup is a collaborative platform created by the European Commission and funded by the European Union via the Interoperability Solutions for Public Administrations (ISA) Programme. It offers several services that aim to help e-Government professionals share their experience with each other and supports them to find, choose, re-use, develop and implement interoperability solutions. Gov2U has used this platform during Y1 for promoting project’s announcements concerning newsletter’s issues and press release availability to the general audience.

3.2.6.2 European Innovation Partnership On Active And Healthy Ageing

This platform is a communication and information hub for all actors involved in Active and Healthy Ageing through Europe; the place to promote news and events, to meet and exchange ideas with peers, to look for potential partners on innovative projects.

Launched in 2011, the [European Innovation Partnership on Active and Healthy Ageing](#) gathers stakeholders from all over Europe committed to increase healthy life expectancy by two years

by 2020. To do so, it works in 6 action groups: adherence, fall prevention, frailty, integrated care, independent living and age-friendly environments.

At the beginning of 2016, all action groups have renewed their action plan and the new one from the age-friendly environments Action Group includes a sub-objective on inclusive smart cities (see https://ec.europa.eu/eip/ageing/actiongroup/index/d4_en). The renewal of the action plans went hand in hand with a new call for commitments which aimed at "inviting organisations from all over the world, involved in developing, promoting or deploying / implementing innovative solutions for active and healthy ageing, to come forward with projects and initiatives that they will implement in the coming 3 years, which are relevant, and can clearly contribute, to the goals and action plans of the existing EIP on AHA Action Groups".

Mobile-Age took this opportunity to commit to support the Action Group on age-friendly environments, and in particular its sub-objective on inclusive smart cities, in order to exchange information on its activities and to share results with the wide range of stakeholders involved in the European Innovation Partnership on Active and Healthy Ageing.

3.2.7 Measurement of effectiveness of communication and dissemination activities

In order to estimate effectiveness of the communication and dissemination activities undertaken by WP5 and the impact of the project's dissemination to the external audience, some indicators were foreseen in the deliverable D5.1 "Communication and Dissemination Plan".

Performance will be continuously monitored against predetermined targets and within the timeframe scheduled in D5.1

<i>Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)</i>	<i>Target established</i>	<i>Current Data (Official measurement Feb.2016 – Jan. 2017)</i>	<i>Who will be responsible for the measurement</i>
Number of Newsletter subscribers	200+	94	Gov2u
Number of visits (sessions) on Mobile-Age website	1,000+	3,036	Gov2u
Number of likes in Facebook, followers in Twitter and connections in LinkedIn	100+	262 (62 likes in Facebook, 165 followers in Twitter and 35 members in LinkedIn group.)	AGE Platform
Press coverage of the project (in radio, TV, newspapers, magazines, informational)	5+	36	AGE Platform

websites)			
Engagement with other similar projects	By M24-M36: engage with at least 10 projects and organize common meetings with 2-3 of them	12 similar projects have accepted Mobile-Age invitation for cross dissemination and collaboration.	Gov2u, AGE Platform

Table 13 : Key performance indicators – measurement of success (Feb.2016 – Jan.2017)

According to table 13, all KPIs have been achieved by the consortium other than the number of subscribers to the Mobile-Age newsletter. For this reason, corrective actions will be followed during the upcoming period (see 3.3) to meet our goals as outlined in D5.1.

3.2.8 Overview of dissemination tools and activities

The following table summarizes all dissemination tools and activities performed during the reporting period.

Type of activity	Number
Number of Page views on Mobile-Age website	8,620
Number of visits (sessions) on Mobile-Age website	3,036
Organization of events	32
Participation in conferences, workshops and events	21
Newsletter Issues	3
Press Releases	1
Liaison with other similar EU funded projects	12
Press Coverage (radio, TV, newspapers, magazines, informational websites)	36
Media Coverage (radio, TV, newspapers, magazines, informational websites, portals, partners' social media, partners' websites, blog posts)	105

Table 14 : Overview of dissemination tools and activities (Feb.2016 – Jan 2017)

3.3 Corrective actions for achieving KPIs in newsletter subscribers

The key performance indicator for Y1 regarding the number of newsletter subscribers as set in D5.1 is 200+, while the achieved number is 94. For this reason, corrective actions will be undertaken for the upcoming period aiming to reach the set number.

However, the distribution of the Mobile-Age newsletter issues has been performed by Gov2u through emails to 349 contacts of stakeholders.

Nowadays, social media is the most powerful channel for reaching desired audiences. Thus, indirectly, the Mobile-Age consortium will try to implement the following actions through social media:

- Gov2u will design and create short stories with “personas” that will be posted on social media. The aim of this action is to attract larger audience through the project’s social media profiles. Partners will try to make them viral through their own profiles and networks.
- Quotes by partners to briefly explain the project and/or its innovative character will be posted on Mobile-Age’s and partners’ social media profiles with a view to attracting more followers and to raise the visibility of the project in social media. The design of these quotes will be undertaken by Gov2u with partners providing appropriate input to this action.
- Project partners will create, short videos (for example, testimonials by senior citizens) from their workshops. Adherence to ethical guidelines which requires the informed consent of senior citizens in advance of recording video material will be respected. With the consent of senior citizens, the videos will be promoted via partners’ communication channels and networks as well as on social media profiles and the local press.

4 Dissemination activities for Year 2

Entering the Y2 of project's implementation, WP5 will continue to plan, implement, coordinate and report dissemination activities for the period M13-M24.

4.1 Dissemination and communication tools

4.1.1 Mobile-Age website

The website will be regularly updated with:

- news articles on project's progress, workshop, meetings, participation in conferences, etc.
- events related to the project;
- promotional material;
- press releases for announcing project's achievements;
- cross dissemination and collaboration with similar projects;
- interesting news across the web related to the project's topic;
- Mobile-Age newsletter issues.

Website analytics will continue to be used to monitor website visibility throughout the project's duration.

4.1.2 Mobile-Age social media

The project social media profiles will be updated on a regular basis with:

- project news and developments;
- project newsletter issues and press releases;
- interesting quotes from partners about the project;
- articles from the web related to project's topic;
- newsletter issues, press releases and other developments from similar projects that have established collaboration in cross dissemination with Mobile-Age.

4.1.3 Newsletter

As mentioned in the DoW the newsletter issues will be published on a quarterly basis. During Y2 will be published 4 issues:

- **Newsletter Issue No. 4** (April 2017)
- **Newsletter Issue No. 5** (July 2017)
- **Newsletter Issue No. 6** (October 2017)
- **Newsletter Issue No. 7** (January 2018)

4.1.4 Collaboration with other similar projects

Gov2u, WP5 leader, will continue its efforts in approaching similar projects and will regularly update established cross dissemination synergies.

4.1.5 Mailing lists

All mailing lists will be regularly updated according to the project's needs and will be used to inform stakeholders on project's developments. Stakeholders will be invited to project's workshops and other relevant events.

4.1.6 Press releases

Press releases will be published to announce major developments on the project during Y2.

4.1.7 Presentations in third party events

Project partners will be encouraged to participate in third party events to promote the project and to raise visibility to target groups and stakeholders.

5 Conclusions

The principal objective of this deliverable is to present dissemination and communication tools and activities that were used to promote the project during Y1.

The main part of the document presents all activities undertaken by the Mobile-Age consortium from February 2016 to January 2017. In addition, the deliverable D5.2 introduces the reader to the project, describes dissemination and communication objectives for the reporting period in detail and outlines the activities that will be performed in the upcoming period M13-M24.

APPENDIX I – Media Coverage

<i>Partner's Name</i>	<i>Type of press item (press release, interview, etc.)</i>	<i>Title of the press item</i>	<i>Media where it was published</i>	<i>URL (if available)</i>
AGE	AGE monthly newsletter CoverAGE	AGE becomes partner in a new project on online public services for older persons	AGE website and distribution to AGE contact list	http://www.age-platform.eu/policy-work/news/age-becomes-partner-new-project-online-public-services-older-persons
Gov2u	Press release	Mobile-Age project: making senior citizens benefit from open government data	Joinup portal	https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/news/mobile-age-project-making-senior-citizens-benefit-open-government-data
Gov2u	Press Release	Mobile-Age project published its 1st Press Release	Gov2u website	http://www.gov2u.org/index.php/learn/updates/308-mobile-age-project
Gov2u	Newsletter Issue No.1	Mobile-Age project: Co-created personalised mobile access to public services for senior citizens - 1st Newsletter Issue now available!	Joinup portal	https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/news/mobile-age-project-co-created-personalised-mobile-access-public-services-senior-citizens-1st-newsletter-issue-now-available
Gov2u	Newsletter Issue No.2	Mobile-Age project: Co-created personalised mobile access to public services for senior citizens – 2nd Newsletter Issue now available!	Joinup portal	https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/news/mobile-age-project-co-created-personalised-mobile-access-public-services-senior-citizens-%E2%80%93-2nd-newsletter-issue-now-available

ifib	Article	Wo geht was in Osterholz?	Newspaper Weser Report	http://www.mobile-age.eu/images/pdf/Article%20Weser-Report_2016-07-06.pdf
ifib	Article	Services für Senioren	New Kommune21	http://www.kommune21.de/meldung_24501_Services+f%C3%BCr+Senioren.html
ifib	Article	Für einen großen Radius im Alter	Newspaper Stadtteil Kurier	http://www.mobile-age.eu/images/pdf/2016-08-22_Stadtteil-Kurier_Suedost_-22-08-2016_(002).pdf
ifib	Article	Online und mobil im Alter	Stadtteil Kurier – Tageszeitung für Bremen und Niedersachsen	http://www.mobile-age.eu/news/58-mobile-age-event-in-osterholz-featured-in-the-weser-kurier-%E2%80%93-tageszeitung-f%C3%BCr-bremen-und-niedersachsen.html
ifib	Article	Offene Daten, Datenaktivismus und Bürgerbeteiligung für den demografischen Wandel	Soziopolis	http://www.soziopolis.de/beobachten/wissenschaft/artikel/offene-daten-datenaktivismus-und-buergerbeteiligung-fuer-den-demografischen-wandel/
ifib	Blog post	Erste Version der MobileAge Anwendung für Osterholz in Benutzung	Ifib blog	http://www.ifib.de/blog/index.php/site/comments/erste-version-der-mobileage-anwendung-fuer-osterholz-in-benutzung
ifib	Blog post	Projekttreffen MobileAge in Bremen	Ifib blog	http://www.ifib.de/blog/index.php/site/comments/projekttreffen-mobileage-in-bremen
ifib	Blog post	Social and technological innovations to help older people realize their potential	Ifib blog	http://www.ifib.de/blog/index.php/site/comments/social-and-technological-innovations-to-help-older-people-realize-their-potential
ifib	Blog post	Workshop in Copenhagen on	Ifib blog	http://www.ifib.de/blog/index.php/site/comments/workshop-in-copenhagen-on

		becoming old in the age of mediatization		orkshop in copenhagen on becoming old in the age of mediatization
ifib	Blog post	MobileAge Anwendung nimmt Gestalt an	Ifib blog	http://www.ifib.de/blog/index.php/site/comments/mobileage_anwendung_nimmt_gestalt_an
ifib	Blog post	Erste Ergebnisse aus MobileAge präsentiert	Ifib blog	http://www.ifib.de/blog/index.php/site/comments/erste_ergebnisse_aus_mobileage_praesentiert
ifib	Blog post	MobileAge beginnt die Anforderungsanalyse	Ifib blog	http://www.ifib.de/blog/index.php/site/comments/mobileage_beginnt_die_anforderungsanalyse
ifib	Blog post	Zweites MobileAge Projekttreffen in Zaragoza	Ifib blog	http://www.ifib.de/blog/index.php/site/comments/zweites_mobileage_projekttreffen_in_zaragoza
ifib	Blog post	MobileAge Auftakt-Workshop im Bremer Stadtteil Osterholz	Ifib blog	http://www.ifib.de/blog/index.php/site/comments/mobileage_auftakt_workshop_im_bremer_stadtteil_osterholz
ifib	Blog post	Osterholzer Seniorinnen und Senioren interessiert an EU-Projekt MobileAge	Ifib blog	http://www.ifib.de/blog/index.php/site/comments/osterholzer_seniorinnen_und_senioren_interessiert_an_eu_projekt_mobileage
ifib	Blog post	Kick-off für neues Open Government Projekt	Ifib blog	http://www.ifib.de/blog/index.php/site/comments/kick_off_fuer_neues_open_government_projekt
ifib	Tweet	#Seniorcitizens in #Bremen have just received their tablets. Final #cocreation phase begins & allows for	Twitter@juliane_jarke	https://twitter.com/juliane_jarke/status/804290240571641856

		innovative #civictech @MobileAgeEU		
ifib	Tweet	Productive meeting with @MobileAgeEU partners. Discussed forthcoming #cocreation in @zaragoza_es and Thessaloniki http://bit.ly/2gG11xu	Twitter@juliane_jarke	https://twitter.com/juliane_jarke/status/803992856763441153
ifib	Tweet	Our article (in German) on #opendata #civictech and #seniorcitizens - based on our research in @MobileAgeEU @ifibGmbH	Twitter@juliane_jarke	https://twitter.com/juliane_jarke/status/803153009047801856
ifib	Tweet	Looking forward to keynote of @Andreas_Hepp & will present insights from @MobileAgeEU at conf on "becoming #old in te age of #mediatization"	Twitter@juliane_jarke	https://twitter.com/juliane_jarke/status/792445214514417664
ifib	Tweet	Unser Artikel über @MobileAgeEU in #Bremen mit #seniorcitizens #civictech gemeinsam entwickeln am @ifibGmbH	Twitter@juliane_jarke	https://twitter.com/juliane_jarke/status/773597493774970880
ifib	Tweet	Über unsere @MobileAgeEU Aktivitäten in #Bremen	Twitter@juliane_jarke	https://twitter.com/juliane_jarke/status/767656573401530368

		berichtet @weserkurier http://bit.ly/2bw61Rt #civictech #opendata		
ifib	Tweet	Thanks to @zaragoza_es for hosting @MobileAgeEU to work on our ideas for #cocreation & #opendata wt #seniorcitizens	Twitter@juliane_jarke	https://twitter.com/juliane_jarke/status/750702701269422080
ifib	Tweet	Arrived in beautiful Zaragoza and look forward to two days of meeting with @MobileAgeEU partners	Twitter@juliane_jarke	https://twitter.com/juliane_jarke/status/750006690209234944
ifib	Tweet	Off to @MobileAgeEU project meeting look forward meeting wt @oeg_upm @tingtun @AGE_Platform EU @Gov2u @CSTOLANCAST ER @FTB_ESV @zaragoza_es...	Twitter@juliane_jarke	https://twitter.com/juliane_jarke/status/749870468392517633
ifib	Tweet	Exploring #Bremen #Osterholz while conducting interviews with senior citizens as part of #cocreation @MobileAgeEU	Twitter@juliane_jarke	https://twitter.com/juliane_jarke/status/747910190524170240
ifib	Tweet	We kicked-off our @MobileAgeEU	Twitter@juliane_jarke	https://twitter.com/juliane_jarke/status/742263014359977984

		#CoCreation activities in #Bremen for #opendata & #civictech http://bit.ly/1U3sYbH		
ifib	Tweet	Our co-creation methodology in @MobileAgeEU is receiving attention.	Twitter@juliane_jarke	https://twitter.com/juliane_jarke/status/741236834336964608
ifib	Tweet	This is our new project: co-creating #opengov services and #opendata with #seniorcitizens -- #civictech	Twitter@juliane_jarke	https://twitter.com/juliane_jarke/status/735023223251869696
ifib	Tweet	Fantastic kick-off meeting of #MobileAge Looking forward to working on #civichacking and #opendata with #seniors	Twitter@juliane_jarke	https://twitter.com/juliane_jarke/status/697682282149257216
ifib	Tweet	MobileAge Anwendung nimmt Gestalt an: Im Rahmen des dreijährigen EU-Projekts MobileAge entwickeln Wissenschaft... http://bit.ly/2drW7ij	Twitter@ifibGmbH	https://twitter.com/ifibGmbH/status/781806007689224192
ifib	Tweet	Erste Ergebnisse aus MobileAge präsentiert: Bei der diesjährigen Konferenz der European Association for	Twitter@ifibGmbH	https://twitter.com/ifibGmbH/status/773261570302291968

		the S... http://bit.ly/2bVmsKU		
ifib	Tweet	MobileAge beginnt die Anforderungsanalyse: Das ifib entwickelt im Rahmen des dreijährigen EU-Projekts MobileA... http://bit.ly/2b5dxjN	Twitter@ifibGmbH	https://twitter.com/ifibGmbH/status/766404247730524160
ifib	Tweet	Zweites MobileAge Projekttreffen in Zaragoza: Vom 5. bis 7. Juli fand das zweite Partner-Treffen des EU-Proje... http://bit.ly/29NHkQJ	Twitter@ifibGmbH	https://twitter.com/ifibGmbH/status/753887898701705216
ifib	Tweet	MobileAge Auftakt-Workshop im Bremer Stadtteil Osterholz: Mit einem Auftakt-Workshop begann das Bremer Team d... http://bit.ly/1Q4gLaj	Twitter@ifibGmbH	https://twitter.com/ifibGmbH/status/743061929850068992
ifib	Tweet	Osterholzer Seniorinnen und Senioren interessiert an EU-Projekt MobileAge: Am vergangenen Montag fand im Orts... http://bit.ly/1TC	Twitter@ifibGmbH	https://twitter.com/ifibGmbH/status/735832497003462656

		9JWv		
ifib	Tweet	Kick-off für neues Open Government Projekt: Vom 9. bis 10. Februar 2016 nahmen wir in Lancaster (GB) am Kick-o... http://bit.ly/1o6bPFB	Twitter@ifibGmbH	https://twitter.com/ifibGmbH/status/697763157352144896
AUTH	Interview	Ο Α. Συμεωνίδης μιλά για το ερευνητικό πρόγραμμα «Mobile-Age» (audio)	ERT radio	http://www.ert.gr/o-a-symeonidis-mila-gia-to-erevniko-programma-mobile-age-audio/
AUTH	Interview	Ανδρέας Συμεωνίδης: Mobile-Age από το ΑΠΘ	Presspublica.gr	http://www.presspublica.gr/%CE%B1%CE%BD%CE%B4%CF%81%CE%AD%CE%B1%CF%82-%CF%83%CF%85%CE%BC%CE%B5%CF%89%CE%BD%CE%AF%CE%B4%CE%B7%CF%82-mobile-age-%CE%B1%CF%80%CF%8C-%CF%84%CE%BF-%CE%B1%CF%80%CE%B8/
AUTH	Article	APPLICATION ΥΓΕΙΑΣ ΓΙΑ ΗΛΙΚΙΩΜΕΝΟΥΣ: e-ενημέρωση για γιατρούς και φαρμακεία	Eleftherostypos.gr	http://www.eleftherostypos.gr/ellada/19131-e-nimerosi-gia-giatrous-kai-farmakeia/
AUTH	Article	Mobile-Age: Μια πολύ απλή εφαρμογή θα βοηθά τους ηλικιωμένους να βρίσκουν το γιατρό τους	Tvxs.gr	http://tvxs.gr/news/ygeia/mobile-age-mia-poly-apli-efarmogi-tha-boitha-toy-ilikiomenoys-na-briskoun-giatro-toys
AUTH	Article	MyOpenMacedonia - Εφαρμογή του ΑΠΘ βοηθά ηλικιωμένους να κλείσουν	in.gr	http://health.in.gr/news/various/article/?aid=1500089575

		ραντεβού στον γιατρό		
AUTH	Article	MyOpenMacedonia - Η νέα εφαρμογή μέσω της οποίας οι ηλικιωμένοι θα κλείνουν ραντεβού στο γιατρό	Dope magazine - online	http://www.dope.gr/myopenmacedonia-%ce%b7-%ce%bd%ce%ad%ce%b1-%ce%b5%cf%86%ce%b1%cf%81%ce%bc%ce%bf%ce%b3%ce%ae-%ce%bc%ce%ad%cf%83%cf%89-%cf%84%ce%b7%cf%82-%ce%bf%cf%80%ce%bf%ce%af%ce%b1%cf%82-%ce%bf%ce%b9/
AUTH	Article	Ραντεβού στο γιατρό και συνταγογράφηση μέσω κινητού για ηλικιωμένους	aftodioikisi.gr	http://www.aftodioikisi.gr/koinonia/rantevou-sto-giatro-kai-sintagografisi-meso-kinitou-gia-ilikiomenous/
AUTH	Article	Ηλικιωμένοι θα κλείνουν ραντεβού στον γιατρό μέσω του mobile app	Athens News Agency - Macedonian Press Agency (ANA-MPA)	http://www.praktoreio-macedonia.gr/article/582/Ilikiomenoi-tha-kleinoun-rantebou-ston-giatro--meso-tou-mobile-app
AUTH	Article	Μέσω mobile app θα κλείνουν πλέον ραντεβού με το γιατρό οι ηλικιωμένοι στην Κεντρική Μακεδονία	Dimosiografiko Sigkrotima Macedonia	http://www.makthes.gr/news/GR/reportage_S/reportage_C/Meso_mobile_app_tha_kleinoun_pleon_rantevou_me_to_giatro_oi_ilikiomenoi_stin_Kentriki_Makedonia
AUTH	Article	Ιατρικό ραντεβού μέσω κινητού	Kilkis24.gr	http://www.kilkis24.gr/%CE%B9%CE%B1%CF%84%CF%81%CE%B9%CE%BA%CF%8C-%CF%81%CE%B1%CE%BD%CF%84%CE%B5%CE%B2%CE%BF%CF%8D-%CE%BC%CE%AD%CF%83%CF%89-%CE%BA%CE%B9%CE%BD%CE%B7%CF%84%CE%BF%CF%8D/
AUTH	Article	Εφαρμογή του ΑΠΘ βοηθά	mynews.gr	http://www.mynews.gr/14/905549/%CE%B5%CF%86%CE%B1%CF%81%CE%BC%

		ηλικιωμένους να κλείσουν ραντεβού στον γιατρό		CE%BF%CE%B3%CE%AE-%CF%84%CE%BF%CF%85-%CE%B1%CF%80%CE%B8-%CE%B2%CE%BF%CE%B7%CE%B8%CE%AC-%CE%B7%CE%BB%CE%B9%CE%BA%CE%B9%CF%89%CE%BC%CE%AD%CE%BD%CE%BF%CF%85%CF%82-%CE%BD%CE%B1-%CE%BA%CE%BB%CE%B5%CE%AF%CF%83%CE%BF%CF%85%CE%BD-%CF%81%CE%B1%CE%BD%CF%84%CE%B5%CE%B2%CE%BF%CF%8D-%CF%83%CF%84%CE%BF%CE%BD-%CE%B3%CE%B9%CE%B1%CF%84%CF%81%CF%8C
AUTH	Article	MyOpenMacedonia: Ένα mobile app συνταγογράφησης φαρμάκων για ηλικιωμένους	onmed.gr	http://www.onmed.gr/ygeia-ena-mobile-app-syntagografis-farmakon-gia-iliikiomenous
AUTH	Article	Εφαρμογή στο κινητό για ραντεβού με τον γιατρό σας ανέπτυξε το ΑΠΘ	ert.gr	http://www.ert.gr/445150-2/
AUTH	Article	Θεσσαλονίκη: Το ΑΠΘ αναπτύσσει app με τη βοήθεια των... ΚΑΠΗ	typosthes.gr	http://www.typosthes.gr/gr/topika/article/103359/thessaloniki-to-apth-anaptussei-app-me-ti-boitheia-ton-kapi/
AUTH	Article	Εφαρμογή στο κινητό για ραντεβού με τον γιατρό σας ανέπτυξε το ΑΠΘ	inewsgr.com	http://www.inewsgr.com/23/efarmogi-sto-kinito-gia-rantevou-me-ton-giatro-sas-aneptyxe-to-apth.htm
AUTH	Article	Πρόσβαση των ηλικιωμένων σε δημόσια ανοιχτά δεδομένα	diorismos.gr	http://www.diorismos.gr/suvvainoun/25170/prosvas-h-twn-hlikiwmenwn-se-dhmosia-anoixta-

		στόχος του ερευνητικού έργου στο ΑΠΘ		dedomena-stoxos-tou-ereunhtikou-ergou-sto-apth
AUTH	Article	Το ερευνητικό πρόγραμμα του ΑΠΘ που διευκολύνει τους ηλικιωμένους να μάθουν τις εφαρμογές κινητών	eteachers.gr	http://www.eteachers.gr/to-erevnitiko-programma-tou-apth-pou-diefkolini-tous-ilikiomenous-na-mathoun-tis-efarmoges-kiniton/
AUTH	Article	Καινοτόμο και πρωτοποριακό πρόγραμμα του ΑΠΘ μαθαίνει σε ηλικιωμένους τα μυστικά της τεχνολογίας!	karfitsa.gr	http://www.karfitsa.gr/2016/07/11/kainotomo-kai-protoporikiako-programm/
AUTH	Article	Καινοτόμο και πρωτοποριακό πρόγραμμα του ΑΠΘ μαθαίνει σε ηλικιωμένους τα μυστικά της τεχνολογίας!	Tromaktiko blogspot	http://tro-maktiko.blogspot.gr/2016/07/blog-post_3631.html?utm_source=feedburner&utm_medium=feed&utm_campaign=Feed:+blogspot/hyMBI+(tromaktiko)
AUTH	Article	Ερευνητικό πρόγραμμα για διευκόλυνση ηλικιωμένων σε εφαρμογές κινητών	gothess.gr	www.gothess.gr/articles/thessaloniki/43483/ereunitiko-programma-gia-dieukolynsi-ilikiomenon-se-efarmoges-kiniton/
AUTH	Article	«MyOpenMacedonia» το mobile app του ΑΠΘ, μέσω του οποίου ηλικιωμένοι θα κλείνουν ραντεβού στον γιατρό και θα συνταγογραφού	halkidikivoice.gr	http://www.halkidikivoice.gr/sthles/tecnologia/item/276-app-apth-farmaka

		ν τα φάρμακά τους		
AUTH	Article	MyOpenMacedonia, το mobile app του ΑΠΘ	nooz.gr	http://www.nooz.gr/tech/myopenmacedonia-to-mobile-app-tou-ap8
AUTH	Article	Hi-tech... παππουδες «φτιαχνει» το ΑΠΘ – Ερευνητικό πρόγραμμα για την προσβαση ηλικιωμενων σε εφαρμογες κινητων	press724.gr	http://press724.gr/hi-tech-%cf%80%ce%b1%cf%80%cf%80%ce%bf%cf%8d%ce%b4%ce%b5%cf%82-%cf%86%cf%84%ce%b9%ce%ac%cf%87%ce%bd%ce%b5%ce%b9-%cf%84%ce%bf-%ce%b1%cf%80%ce%b8-%ce%b5%cf%81%ce%b5%cf%85%ce%bd%ce%b7%cf%84/
AUTH	Radio interview, 12th of July 2016		FM100 Thessaloniki	n/a
AUTH	Radio interview, 12th of July 2016		98.4FM Athens	n/a
AUTH	Radio interview, 13th of July 2016		ERT - Proto programma, ert.gr	http://www.ert.gr/o-a-symeonidis-mila-gia-to-erevniko-programma-mobile-age-audio/
AUTH	Radio interview, 13th of July 2016		FM100 Thessaloniki	n/a
AUTH	Radio interview, 13th of July 2016		Alpha Radio	n/a
AUTH	TV Interview, 18th of July 2016		Proini Zoni - TV magazino	n/a
RCM	Article	Έργο Mobile-Age για τους ηλικιωμένους που μένουν μόνοι τους	Newsbeast.gr	http://www.newsbeast.gr/greece/arthro/2126540/er-go-mobile-age-gia-tous-iliikiomenous-pou-menoun-moni-tous
UPM	News (español)	Mobile-Age, datos abiertos y tecnología para	Web UPM	http://www.upm.es/UPM/CanalUPM/Noticias de investigacion?id=f4e8e8a8ba1

		los mayores		f4510VgnVCM10000009c7648aR&fmt=detail&prefmt=articulo
UPM	News (inglés)	Mobile-Age project: making senior citizens benefit from open government data	Web UPM	http://www.upm.es/internacional/UPM/UPM_Channel/News/52afe63c01105510VgnVCM10000009c7648aR_CRD
UPM	News (español)	Mobile-Age, datos abiertos y tecnología para los mayores, de la mano del OEG	Web OEG	http://www.oeg-upm.net/index.php/es/last-news/399-mobile-age-senior-citizens-open-government-data/index.html
UPM	News (inglés)	Mobile-Age, making senior citizens benefit from open government data	Web OEG	http://www.oeg-upm.net/index.php/en/last-news/399-mobile-age-senior-citizens-open-government-data/index.html
UPM	Tweet on Published News	Para "seniors" #Tecnología y #datosabiertos @MobileAgeEU en http://www.oeg-upm.net/index.php/es/last-news/399-mobile-age-senior-citizens-open-government-data/index.html ... @oeg_upm @informaticaupm @La_UPM	Twitter OEG	https://twitter.com/oeg_upm/status/739743563748106240
UPM	News	Datos abiertos y tecnología para la los mayores: proyecto Mobile-Age	Blog ODI	http://madrid.theodi.org/2016/06/02/datos-abiertos-y-tecnologia-para-la-poblacion-senior-proyecto-mobile-age/

UPM	Tweet on Published News	Tecnología y #opendata para los mayores desde @oeg_upm en @informaticaupm http://bit.ly/1O17oHL cc @MobileAgeEU	Twitter ODI	https://twitter.com/odi_madrid/status/737582665205878784
UPM	Tweet on Published News	Proyecto Mobile Age, datos abiertos y tecnología para tercera edad. @informaticaupm participa a través de @oeg_upm. http://bit.ly/20QlBsn	Twitter FI	https://twitter.com/informaticaupm/status/737248523826176001
UPM	Link en LinkedIn	Mobile-Age, datos abiertos y tecnología para los mayores	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ontology-engineering-group-universidad-polit-cnica-de-madrid/comments?topic=6143342396815007744&type=U&scope=1957150&stype=C&a=tYj3
UPM	Tweet on Web Mobile-Age	We kicked-off our @MobileAgeEU #CoCreation activities in #Bremen for #opendata & #civictech http://bit.ly/1U3sYbH	Twitter	https://twitter.com/julianejarke/status/742263014359977984
FTB	Project short description (German), 23rd of February 2016	Projekt Mobile-Age	FTB's website	http://ftb-esv.de/mobileage.html
FTB	News, February 2016	Mobile Informationen für mobile	FTB's website	http://ftb-esv.de/newsmobileage.html

		Senioren		
FTB	News, 8th of June 2016	Europäisches Projekt Mobile-Age geht an die Öffentlichkeit	FTB's website	http://ftb-esv.de/newsmobileage2.html
FTB	Project short description (English), 9th of June 2016	Project Mobile-Age	FTB's website	http://ftb-net.com/mobileage.html
FTB	News, 3rd of November 2016	Gemeinsame App-Entwicklung mit Senioren	FTB's website	http://ftb-esv.de/gemeinsameapp-entwicklungmitsenioren.html
Ayuntamiento Zaragoza	Press release	El Ayuntamiento de Zaragoza colabora en un proyecto multinacional para el desarrollo de servicios accesibles a través de móviles que faciliten la vida de los mayores	Web zaragoza.es	http://www.zaragoza.es/ciudad/noticias/detalle_Noticia?id=223549
Ayuntamiento de Zaragoza	Press release	Zaragoza, pionera en Europa sobre el desarrollo de servicios públicos accesibles a través de móviles para las personas mayores	Web zaragoza.es	http://www.zaragoza.es/ciudad/noticias/detalle_Noticia?id=223780
Ayuntamiento de Zaragoza	Facebook Post		Facebook Ayuntamiento de Zaragoza	https://www.facebook.com/ayuntamientodezaragoza/photos/a.10150115326379873.287968.191888594872/10154479471909873/?type=3
Ayuntamiento de Zaragoza	News	Los mayores de Zaragoza, en un	Heraldo de Aragón	http://www.heraldo.es/noticias/aragon/zaragoza-

		proyecto para mejorar su aprovechamiento de las nuevas tecnologías		provincia/zaragoza/2016/05/24/los-mayores-zaragoza-proyecto-para-mejorar-aprovechamiento-las-nuevas-tecnologias-876317-301.html
Ayuntamiento de Zaragoza	Radio Podcast	Proyecto Europeo Mobile-Age	Aragón Radio	http://www.aragonradio.es/podcast/emision/proyecto-europeo-mobile-age/
Ayuntamiento de Zaragoza	Post on Facebook	Mobile-Age, un proyecto para acercar las nuevas tecnologías a los mayores	Facebook Ayuntamiento de Zaragoza	https://www.facebook.com/ayuntamientodezaragoza/posts/10154369276964873
Ayuntamiento de Zaragoza	Tweet	Hoy acogemos a delegaciones de Bremen, Lancaster y Tesalónica en una mesa de trabajo del proyecto europeo para personas mayores @MobileAgeEU	Twitter @zaragoza_es	n/a
Ayuntamiento de Zaragoza	Tweet	Zaragoza acoge a expertos de @MobileAgeEU para crear servicios públicos accesibles a través de móviles para mayores.		n/a
Ayuntamiento de Zaragoza	Tweet	Planteamos ejemplos como @MobileAgeEU en nuestra gestión de #DatosAbiertos		n/a

		en la mesa del @opencities2016 #opencitiessummit #IODC16		
Ayuntamiento de Zaragoza	Tweet	#Estapasando @zaragoza_es presenta su participación en el proyecto europeo @MobileAgeEU en el @opendatacon #IODC16		n/a

Table 15 : Media coverage

APPENDIX II – Google Analytics

Below the reader may find the most important data related to the website. The data are also mention in section

Figure 1 : Audience Overview (May 2016 – January 2017)

D5.2 First Communication and Dissemination Report

Figure 2 : Location Overview

APPENDIX III – Facebook Insights

Total Page Likes is the number of how many ‘Likes’ your Facebook Page obtained. The figure below provides this information.

Figure 3 : Total Page Likes

Post Reach is the number of people your posts were served to and it is depicted on the following figure.

Figure 4 : Post reach

Average reach is the success of different post types based on average reach and engagement.

Figure 5 : Average reach

Total Reach is the number of people who were served any activity from your Page including your posts to your Page by other people, Page likes ads, mentions and checkins.

Figure 6 : Total reach

Reactions are likes and other ways people to react to your Page posts. The following figure depicts the types and the number of reactions.

Figure 7 : Reactions

06/13/2016 3:40 pm	Mobile Age just kicked-off its first workshop in Bremen, German			35		12 4		Boost Post
05/30/2016 12:33 pm	Last Monday, the first information event about Mobile Age took pl			29		4 3		Boost Post
05/23/2016 9:07 pm	#PressRelease Launch of the Mobile Age project: making senior			513		4 6		Boost Post
05/19/2016 4:48 pm	Great news! Mobile Age commitment to the European Innovatio			49		1 2		Boost Post
05/19/2016 10:22 am	Interested in population ageing, open data, e-government and a			24		0 1		Boost Post

Figure 8 : The post that most people reached within the reporting period (23 May 2016)

People reached is the number of people your post was served to in the past 28 days.

Figure 9 : People reached

APPENDIX IV - Twitter Profile Summary by Hootsuite

Hootsuite is a Social Media Management System that helps its users to keep track and manage their social network channels. Multiple networks such as Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and Google+ can be managed at the same time. Moreover, in its free version, provides Analytic tools for users' profiles. Free profile summary report can be retrieved for longer periods in comparison to Twitter Analytics and other tools for this social media network.

Below the profile summary of Mobile-Age is presented for the reporting period (Feb. 2016 - Jan. 2017):

Figure 10 : Profile Summary

Appendix V – Newsletter Structure

Figure 11 : Editorial

Figure 12 : Project News

Figure 13 : Other News

Figure 14 : Upcoming events and conferences

Figure 15 : Interesting Publications

Figure 16 : Newsletter Footer

Appendix VI – Promotional Materials

Delivering open and personalised mobile access to public services for senior citizens

At a Glance	The concept
<p>Title: Mobile Age Call Identifier: H2020-INSO-2015: CNECT Topic: INSO-1-2015: ICT-enabled open government Total Budget: €2,923,993.75 Project duration: 36 months Start Date: February 1st, 2016 Project Coordinator: LANCASTER UNIVERSITY (UK) Consortium: TINGTUN AS (TT), AGE PLATFORM EUROPE AISBL (AGE), EVANGELISCHE STIFTUNG VOLMARSTEIN (FTB), GOVERNMENT TO YOU (GOV2U), INSTITUT FÜR INFORMATIONS-MANAGEMENT BREMEN GMBH (IfB), ARISTOTELLO PANEPITIMIO THESSALONIKIS (AUTH), UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE MADRID (UPM), AYUNTAMIENTO DE ZARAGOZA (ZGZ), REGION OF CENTRAL MACEDONIA (RCM). Project Website: www.mobile-age.eu Keywords: ageing society, digital divide, social inclusion, age-friendly environments, older persons, independent living, mobility, safety, accessibility, health information, open data, open governments, public services, apps, e-government, transparency, participatory design, user analytics, civic technology</p>	<p>Mobile Age works on digital mobile applications, based on open data, helping senior citizens access public services in their community in an easier, more personalised and efficient way. Such mobile applications will be tested in four pilot sites in Europe (UK, Germany, Spain and Greece).</p> <p>Older persons' needs and expectations towards digital services are rarely understood. In order to cope with this, Mobile Age is based on the concept of co-creation and will develop mobile open government services that are created together with senior citizens. This means that older persons themselves will decide which services they want to access, which kind of applications they would like to use, and which requirements in terms of accessibility and mobility they set for. This will allow citizens, in particular senior citizens, to become part of what we call open government (online access to public services and information using open data), which will be mutually shaped by older persons, empowered to improve the quality of life in their communities.</p> <p>Mobile Age ensures the inclusion of seniors in digital services, eases their administrative tasks thanks to user-friendly applications, and supports their access to civic participation, active ageing and their involvement in developing age-friendly communities. The project will also increase transparency and trust in public administration through sharing and reuse public information.</p> <p>From concept to innovations</p> <p>The project will be implemented in four pilot sites, which are very complementary in terms of local/regional authority, urban/rural features, and the presence of experts/new comers on e-government: South Lakeland [UK]; Bremen [Germany]; Region of Central Macedonia [Greece]; and Zaragoza [Spain].</p> <p>Each one of these four pilot sites will work on a specific use case of relevance for seniors' citizens: social inclusion (Bremen), extending independent living (South Lakeland), a safe and accessible city for seniors (Zaragoza) and personal health information (Central Macedonia).</p>

Pilot Site	Topic/Case of relevance
Bremen (DE)	Social inclusion
South Lakeland (UK)	Extending Independent Living
Zaragoza (ES)	Safe & accessible city for elderly people
Central Macedonia (GR)	Personal health information

To concretise this, the project will work on two streams:

- The **process innovation**, where studies on co-creation methodologies and open data based public services will be analysed, co-creation activities (workshops, surveys) will be organised, and an evaluation and impact assessment framework as well as policy recommendations will be developed;
- The **technical innovation**, where developers work on the technical platform and software to be used to develop the mobile applications, based on the outcomes of the co-creation activities.

Both streams will work in a complementary way: focusing on the process will allow understanding the needs of users and their behaviours in their contexts, while the technical component will ensure the integration of users' needs in the mobile applications as well as the transferability of data, thus supporting both the dissemination, scale-up and transferability of the project's findings.

Throughout the project, particular attention will be paid to:

- The use of available open data to provide citizens with location-based information and better access to on-line public services;
- The personalisation of access means to public services through user profiles that automatically adapt the content to the citizen's preferences in terms of type of information, presentation and accessibility;
- The integration of disparate public services and sources of information into a single entry point;
- The availability of the mobile application on different devices and in diverse situations (outdoors, in transit, at home, etc.);
- The project team will also analyse users' behaviours on the applications to gain an insight into the opportunities and challenges seniors experience when using mobile technology.

Three innovations offered by Mobile Age

The project will firstly produce digital applications to be used and scaled-up in local authorities throughout Europe. To do so, it will make sure that its technical innovative platform, the **Open Senior Citizen Public Service Engagement Platform (OSCPSEP)** used to build the applications will be re-used in other contexts and by other public authorities.

Moreover, it will compile a **Best Practice Guide for Co-Creation of Open Public Services** and publish policy briefings targeting European, national, regional and local public authorities.

Mobile Age will also publish a framework for impact assessment and evaluation for co-creation approaches in the field of open public services for older persons.

Stay in touch!

www.mobile-age.eu
 info@mobile-age.eu

https://www.facebook.com/mobileageeu/

https://twitter.com/MobileAgeU

https://www.linkedin.com/group/home?gid=8475752

Figure 17 : Project's Factsheet

Co-created personalised mobile access to public services for senior citizens

Project Consortium	Research Objectives	Process innovation	Technical innovation																		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lancaster University (ULANC) Tingtun AS (TT) AGE-Platform Europe (AGE) Evangelische Stiftung Volmarstein/ Forschungsinstitut Technologie und Behinderung (FTB) Government To You Institut Fur Informationsmanagement Bremen GMBH (IfB) Aristotello Panepitismo Thessalonikis (AUTH) Universidad Politecnica de Madrid (UPM) Ayunmiento de Zaragoza (ZGZ) Region of Central Macedonia (RCM) 	<p>Explore and implement innovative ways to support senior citizens to access and use public services through personal mobile technologies and based on open government data.</p> <p>Develop and deploy co-creation approaches and methodologies to engage senior citizens effectively in order to realize the benefits of open government data and mobile technologies for the ageing population.</p> <p>Develop a situated, practice-based understanding of accessibility, mobility and usability of services. Based on this knowledge we will develop a best practice guide and toolkit for service and technology design together with senior citizens.</p> <p>Develop a framework for impact assessment and evaluation for co-creation approaches to open service development for the ageing population.</p>	<p>Phase I 1.1 Preliminary analysis of requirements 1.2 Software development of October</p> <p>Phase II 2.1 Co-creation open, mobile services, requirements and involving co-creation methods 2.2 Personalized Mobile Service Development 2.3 Open data development 2.4 Open data development</p> <p>Phase III 3.1 Evaluation and reuse 3.2 Evaluation of open research results</p>	<p>Month 1-6</p> <p>Month 6-12</p> <p>Month 12-18</p> <p>Month 18-24</p> <p>Month 24-30</p> <p>Month 30-36</p>																		
<p>Project Details</p> <p>Instrument: INSO-1-2015: ICT - enabled open government Total Cost: €2,923,993.75 Duration: 36 months Start Date: 1st February 2016</p> <p>Project Coordinator: Prof Niall Hayes Lancaster University</p> <p>Project Contact: Dr. Bev Abram Lancaster University</p> <p>Tel: +44 (0)1524 510507 b.abram@lancaster.ac.uk</p> <p>Contact us: info@mobile-age.eu</p>	<p>Use Case Scenarios across Europe</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%;"> <thead> <tr> <th>Use Case ID</th> <th>Social Inclusion</th> <th>Extending Independent Living</th> <th>A safe and accessible city for elderly people</th> <th>Personal Health Information</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Mobile Services</td> <td>Map-based social networking and mobile open information services</td> <td>Assessing the needs of senior citizens to extend independent living</td> <td>Map-based data curation and collaborative map creation</td> <td>Health-related open data information services for senior citizens</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Problem Domain</td> <td>Connecting people, open data & place through social networking for senior citizens</td> <td>Assessing and tracking the service provision for elderly citizens to support their independent living</td> <td>Empowering elderly people to create collaboratively maps with accessible routes, alert city</td> <td>Consuming open data feeds for senior citizens</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Trial Sites</td> <td>Map-based social networking and mobile open information services</td> <td>Assessing the needs of senior citizens to extend independent living</td> <td>Map-based data curation and collaborative map creation</td> <td>Health-related open data information services for senior citizens</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Use Case ID	Social Inclusion	Extending Independent Living	A safe and accessible city for elderly people	Personal Health Information	Mobile Services	Map-based social networking and mobile open information services	Assessing the needs of senior citizens to extend independent living	Map-based data curation and collaborative map creation	Health-related open data information services for senior citizens	Problem Domain	Connecting people, open data & place through social networking for senior citizens	Assessing and tracking the service provision for elderly citizens to support their independent living	Empowering elderly people to create collaboratively maps with accessible routes, alert city	Consuming open data feeds for senior citizens	Trial Sites	Map-based social networking and mobile open information services	Assessing the needs of senior citizens to extend independent living	Map-based data curation and collaborative map creation	Health-related open data information services for senior citizens
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Figure 18 : Project's Academic Poster

WHO IS INVOLVED?

Project Duration:
36 months

Start date:
February 2016

Project Coordinator:
University of Lancaster, UK

Delivering open and personalised mobile access to public services for senior citizens

Get in touch with us:

info@mobile-age.eu

<https://www.facebook.com/mobileageeu>

<https://twitter.com/MobileAgeEU>

<https://www.linkedin.com/grp/home?gid=8475752>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 69319

www.mobile-age.eu

OUR METHODOLOGY

To concretise this, the project will work on two streams:

- ✓ The process innovation, to carry out studies on co-creation methodologies and open data based public services, organise co-creation activities (workshops, surveys) and develop an evaluation and impact assessment framework as well as policy recommendations developed
- ✓ The technical innovation, to develop a technical platform, software and mobile applications, based on the outcomes of the co-creation activities

Streams will work in a complementary way: focusing on the process innovation will allow understanding the needs of users and their behaviours in their contexts, while the technical component will ensure the integration of users' needs in the mobile applications as well as the transferability of data, thus supporting both the dissemination, scale-up and transferability of the project's findings.

EXPECTED OUTCOMES

The project will firstly produce digital applications to be used and scaled-up in local authorities throughout Europe. To do so, it will make sure that its technical innovative platform, the Open Senior Citizen Public Service Engagement Platform (OSCPSEP) used to build the applications will be re-used in other contexts and by other public authorities.

Moreover, it will compile a **Best Practice Guide for Co-Creation of Open Public Services** and publish policy briefings targeting European, national, regional and local public authorities.

Mobile Age will also publish a **framework for impact assessment and evaluation for co-creation approaches in the field of open public services for older persons.**

GENERAL OBJECTIVE

Mobile Age develops digital mobile applications, based on open data, helping senior citizens access public services in their community in an easier, more personalised and efficient way. Such mobile applications will be tested in four pilot sites in Europe (UK, Germany, Spain and Greece).

The four pilot sites will focus on a specific theme of relevance for seniors' citizens:

- ✓ social inclusion (Bremen)
- ✓ extending independent living (South Lakeland)
- ✓ a safe and accessible city for seniors (Zaragoza)
- ✓ personal health information (Central Macedonia)

Mobile Age is based on the concept of co-creation. This means that older persons themselves will decide which services they want to access, which kind of applications they would like to use, and which requirements in terms of accessibility and mobility they opt for. This will allow citizens, in particular senior citizens, to become part of what we call open government.

BENEFITS

Mobile Age project will bring clear added value for citizens, policy-makers, public authorities, civil society organisations, open data advocates, researchers and developers. Contact us to be kept informed about the project's developments!

Figure 19 : Project's Brochure

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Figure 20 : Project's Poster

Figure 21 : Project's short Poster

Figure 22 : Overall Project Presentation

Figure 23 : Booklet (for ifib's workshops)

Figure 24 : Project's Logo in German

Delivering open and personalised
mobile access to public services for senior citizens

Invitation / Reminder

- Would you like to learn to use your mobile phone or tablet computer to find out more about local activities that you enjoy attending?
- Would you like to find out how to find information on public services that are important to you?

You do not have to be a computer specialist.

If you are 55 years or above, interested in the internet and want to explore how easy or difficult it is to find information that you want on public services and entertainment in the South Lakes area, we would welcome your opinions.

Just stop by for a coffee and cake to our event on:

Tuesday, June 21, 2016 from **2:00pm to 4:00pm** **and/or** **Friday, June 24, 2016**
at the **Gateway Centre** from **10:00am to 12:00noon**
at the **Gateway Centre**

*(located together with Captain French Surgery),
Gillinggate Centre, Gillinggate, Kendal LA9 4JE.*

Stay in touch!

www.mobile-age.eu info@mobile-age.eu

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 693319

Figure 25 : Invitation for UNLAC's workshop in South Lake

Figure 26 : Personas (ifib's workshops)

Figure 27 : Map of Osterholz (ifib's workshops)

Welches Gerät war DIE Revolution für Ihren Alltag?

Wie sieht Osterholz für Sie in der Zukunft aus?

Früher war alles besser?!

Figure 28 : Postcards (for ifib's workshops)

MobileAge
Mobile Onlinedienste
für und mit Seniorinnen und Senioren gemeinsam entwickeln

Unser Forschungsteam besteht aus Juliane Jarke, Herbert Kubicek und Ulrike Gerhard vom Institut für Informationsmanagement Bremen GmbH (ifib) an der Universität Bremen, sowie Helmut Heck, Frank Reins, Frank Berker und Annika Nietzko vom Forschungsinstitut Technologie und Behinderung (FTB) in Wetter/Ruhr. Das Forschungsvorhaben ist Teil des EU-geförderten Projekts MobileAge (Mobil im Alter) und wird von der Universität Lancaster in Großbritannien koordiniert. Der Projektkoordinator ist Niall Hayes.

Worum geht es in dem Forschungsprojekt?

Das Projekt MobileAge will Seniorinnen und Senioren wie Ihnen (typischerweise 55 Jahre und älter) beim effizienten und effektiven Zugang zu öffentlichen Diensten durch die Nutzung mobiler Technologien (z.B. Smartphones und Tablets) unterstützen. Wir werden ein System entwickeln, das aus einer Anwendung (App) besteht, die auf Tablets und Smartphones genutzt werden kann. Der Fokus unserer Anwendung liegt auf der Verbesserung der selbstbestimmten Teilhabe am öffentlichen Leben von Bremer Seniorinnen und Senioren. Ein wesentlicher Teil unseres Projekts ist es mit Ihnen zusammenzuarbeiten, um zu definieren, wie dieses Ziel erreicht werden kann.

Was ist das Ziel der Studie?

Das Ziel der Studie ist es, innovative Formen des erleichterten Zugangs zu und der Nutzung von öffentlichen Dienstleistungen durch offene Verwaltungsdaten und personalisierte Mobiltechnologien für Seniorinnen und Senioren zu erproben und umzusetzen. Offene Daten sind von Verwaltungen und Privatunternehmen zur Veröffentlichung freigegebene Daten (z.B. Busfahrpläne, Müllabfuhrkalender). Sie sind für jede und jeden frei verfügbar und (weiter) verwendbar. Der zu entwickelnde mobile Onlinedienst wird gemeinschaftlich gestaltet. Seniorinnen und Senioren, lokale Verwaltungen sowie ggf. weitere Organisationen und Dienstleister werden an Interviews, Gruppendiskussionen und Werkstätten teilnehmen. Bei diesen Veran-

Informationsblatt für Teilnehmerinnen und Teilnehmer im Projekt
Mobile Age (Mobil im Alter)

www.mobile-age.eu

Figure 29 : Project Info sheet in German

Figure 30 : Overview of stakeholders

Figure 31 : Workshop Diary

Figure 32 : Rollout

APPENDIX VII – Invitations sent to similar EU funded projects

<i>Project</i>	<i>Action</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Website</i>
FrailSafe project	Horizon 2020 funded project	Ageing, clinical status of frailty	http://www.frailsafe-project.eu
my-AHA (my Active and Healthy Ageing) project	Horizon 2020 funded project	ICT-based platform, empower older citizens to better manage their own health	http://www.activeageing.unito.it/
ECOMODE project	Horizon 2020 funded project	Touch-less mobile devices usable also by older adults and visually impaired people for handling every day issues using ICT	http://www.ecomode-project.eu/index.php
3D Tune-In	Horizon 2020 funded project	Digital games in the field of hearing aid technologies and hearing loss in children and older adults, addressing social inclusion, generating new markets and creating job opportunities	http://3d-tune-in.eu/
RAPP	FP7 funded project	Applications that will enable robots to understand and respond to the intentions and needs of people at risk of exclusion, and especially the elderly.	http://rapp-project.eu/
CogniWin	AAL Joint Programme (ACTIVE AND ASSISTED LIVING PROGRAMME)	Supporting and motivating older adults that work on computerized activities to remain active and productive by providing personalized learning assistance and well-being guidance, enables older adults to maintain or even increase their efficiency and effectiveness at work	http://www.cogniwin.eu/
GIVE & TAKE	AAL Joint Programme	Digital platform that enables senior citizens to	http://givetake.eu/

	(ACTIVE AND ASSISTED LIVING PROGRAMME)	reciprocally exchange services and resources, creating new opportunities for senior citizens to contribute to society as volunteers and caregivers in their local communities.	
ANIMATE	AAL Joint Programme (ACTIVE AND ASSISTED LIVING PROGRAMME)	Older adults participating in ANIMATE benefit by the experience of passing on their knowledge and experience and in return, have the opportunity to learn about new devices and technologies while the company achieves the training and development of its staff.	http://animate-aal.eu/
ENSAFE	AAL Joint Programme (ACTIVE AND ASSISTED LIVING PROGRAMME)	The elderly person is expected to gain more awareness and control over their own health and wellness, empowering them in the self-management of care and thus fostering chances of more independent and higher quality life.	http://www.ensafe-aal.eu/home/
HEREiAM	AAL Joint Programme (ACTIVE AND ASSISTED LIVING PROGRAMME)	Elderly people's independence and active participation, by developing an innovative user-friendly technology able to help them during daily activities	http://www.hereiamproject.org/
CAMI	AAL Joint Programme (ACTIVE AND ASSISTED LIVING PROGRAMME)	Allows older adults to self-manage their daily life and prolong their involvement in the society while allowing their informal caregivers to continue working whilst caring for	http://www.camiproject.eu/

		their loved ones.	
iCareCoops	AAL Joint Programme (ACTIVE AND ASSISTED LIVING PROGRAMME)	Promoting and supporting elderly care cooperatives as a model to organise elderly care in an efficient way.	http://project.icarecoops.eu/
Experience keep people active – ExpAct	AAL Joint Programme (ACTIVE AND ASSISTED LIVING PROGRAMME)	Facilitating the preservation and transfer of older people’s experience and know-how for the benefit of future generations, older people stay engaged in social activities that support healthy and active ageing	http://yama.sml.zhaw.ch/expact/
CoME	AAL Joint Programme (ACTIVE AND ASSISTED LIVING PROGRAMME)	Reduce the number of seniors that demand care services by way of disease prevention and health self-management.	http://www.aal-europe.eu/projects/come/
FairCare	AAL Joint Programme (ACTIVE AND ASSISTED LIVING PROGRAMME)	A platform improves the communication between professional carers, everyday services, volunteers, elderly people and their families.	http://www.fair-care.eu/
SENIOR-TV	AAL Joint Programme (ACTIVE AND ASSISTED LIVING PROGRAMME)	A platform for providing formal and informal caregiving services to older adults that live alone in their own homes, at low cost, and that focuses on the active prevention and the maintenance of relationships with friends, family, and the community	http://www.aal-europe.eu/projects/senior-tv/ , http://seniortv-aal.eu/
OLA	AAL Joint Programme (ACTIVE AND ASSISTED LIVING PROGRAMME)	Supports instrumental activities related to the daily living needs of older adults allowing them to be more independent, self-assured and to have a healthier, safer and organized lifestyle.	http://ola.istar.iscte-iul.pt/wp/
STAGE	AAL Joint Programme (ACTIVE AND	ICT platform that will allow older people to access a selection of cultural events	http://www.aal-europe.eu/projects/stage/

	ASSISTED LIVING PROGRAMME)	provided via streaming by a EU network of entities and stakeholder, social involvement	
SmartBEAT	AAL Joint Programme (ACTIVE AND ASSISTED LIVING PROGRAMME)	Supporting senior Heart Failure patients, their family, relatives and friends, cardiologists and general healthcare professionals accessing innovative ICT solutions that promote an easier, wider and sustainable access to healthcare	http://www.smartbeatproject.org/
ELF@Home	AAL Joint Programme (ACTIVE AND ASSISTED LIVING PROGRAMME)	A self-care solution based on self-check of health conditions and fitness at home. The solution will use an autonomous fitness system targeting not frailty or pre-frailty elder people aged over 65 years and living independently at home.	http://elfathome.eu/
Innovage	Interregional Cooperation Programme INTERREG IVC, financed by the European Union's Regional Development Fund	INNOVAge project aims to help older people to live independently for longer in their own homes by increasing their autonomy and by emerging of new 'technological supply chains' associated with new developments like independent living and eco-innovation, with a valuable contribution to minimize environmental impact of elderly daily life activities.	http://www.innovage-project.eu
MOPACT - Mobilizing The Potential of Active Ageing in Europe	FP7 funded project	The MOPACT project will provide the evidence upon which Europe can begin to make longevity an asset for social and economic development. The project draws together a multidisciplinary team to target the key challenges of ageing.	http://mopact.group.shef.ac.uk/

<p>PERSSILAA: PERsonalised ICT Supported Service for Independent Living and Active Ageing</p>	<p>FP7 funded project</p>	<p>PERSSILAA is a unique project that aims to develop and validate a new service model to screen for and prevent frailty in community dwelling older adults. PERSSILAA stands for PERsonalised ICT Supported Service for Independent Living and Active Ageing. This multimodal service model, focusing on nutrition, physical and cognitive function, is supported by an interoperable ICT service infrastructure, utilising intelligent decision support systems and gamification. Offered to older adults (> 65 years) through local community service, PERSSILAA will be seamlessly integrated with health care services.</p>	<p>http://www.perssilaa.eu/</p>
<p>DoReMi project - Decrease of cOgnitive decline, malnutRition and sedEntariness by elderly empowerment in lifestyle Management and social Inclusion</p>	<p>FP7 funded project</p>	<p>The project aims to develop a systemic solution for older people, which is able to prolong their functional and cognitive capacity by empowering, stimulating and unobtrusively monitoring their daily activities. The project joins together the concept of prevention, centred on the older population with a constructive interaction between mind, body and social engagement. To fulfil these goals, food intake measurements and personalized metabolic control, exergames associated with social interaction stimulation, and cognitive training programs will be introduced to a group of older participants taking part in a pilot study.</p>	<p>http://www.doremi-fp7.eu/</p>

<p>European Cinema for Active Ageing - CINAGE</p>	<p>This project has been funded with support from the European Commission, Lifelong Learning Programme</p>	<p>CINAGE offers exciting later life learning opportunities, engaging elderly people with critical analysis of European cinema and practical film making experience, and thus promoting Active Ageing.</p>	<p>http://cinageproject.eu/en/</p>
<p>Peer-to-Peer Support Fostering Active Ageing Project</p>	<p>The project work started in April 2014, the project runs until 2016 and is funded by the EACEA (European Agency for Education, Culture and Audiovisual Media) of the Lifelong Learning.</p>	<p>The purpose of the project is to work in the field of active ageing, because life expectancy in Europe is getting longer and we have many people who have already achieved well-deserved retirement, but are still youthful, active and vital.</p>	<p>http://www.activeageingproject.eu</p>
<p>ehcoBUTLER</p>	<p>Horizon 2020 funded project</p>	<p>An open digital platform for apps that help older people to live actively and healthily For many people ageing comes with physical or mild cognitive impairments</p>	<p>http://ehcobutler.eu/</p>
<p>Do CHANGE - Do Cardiac Health Advanced New Generation Ecosystem</p>	<p>Horizon 2020 funded project and Taiwanese Government</p>	<p>Empowering individuals with tools and services that optimally monitor and manage their real-time condition. Patients will therefore become stakeholders in their own health and disease management.</p>	<p>http://www.do-change.eu/</p>
<p>IN LIFE - INdependent Living support Functions for the Elderly</p>	<p>Horizon 2020 funded project</p>	<p>Offers all-around, personalised, multi-faceted existing ICT solutions and services addressing diverse daily activities (eating, physical activity, commuting, mental stimulation, communication, social interaction, etc.) to users with cognitive impairment</p>	<p>http://www.inlife-project.eu/</p>

		<p>living in their own home or in sheltered homes, as well as to their formal and informal carers.</p> <p>Emphasis is placed on elderly and carer interactions, communications and care scheduling and monitoring.</p>	
ICT4LIFE	Horizon 2020 funded project	Provides new services for integrated care employing user-friendly ICT tools, ultimately increasing patients with Parkinson's, Alzheimer's and other dementias and their caregivers' quality of life and autonomy at home.	http://www.ict4life.eu/
ENRICHME: ENabling Robot and assisted living environment for Independent Care and Health Monitoring of the Elderly	Horizon 2020 funded project	Enriching the day-to-day experiences of elderly people at home by means of technologies that enable health monitoring, complementary care and social support, helping them to remain active and independent for longer and to enhance their quality of life.	http://www.enrichme.eu/wordpress/
PreventIT	Horizon 2020 funded project	Develops mobile technology that enables early identification of risk factors for functional decline in younger older adults, and empowers them to self-manage their own health and function by adopting a healthy, active lifestyle.	http://www.preventit.eu/
SUSTAIN	Horizon 2020 funded project	Aims to improve integrated care for older people living at home with multiple health and social care needs.	http://www.sustain-eu.org/
Prosperity4All	FP7 funded project	Develops the infrastructure to allow a new ecosystem to grow; one that is based	http://www.prosperity4all.eu/

		on self-rewarding collaboration, that can reduce redundant development, lower costs, increase market reach and penetration internationally, and create the robust cross-platform spectrum of mainstream and assistive technology based access solutions required.	
MOPACT	FP7 funded project	Provides the research and practical evidence upon which Europe can begin to make longevity an asset for social and economic development.	http://mopact.group.shef.ac.uk/
ROUTE-TO-PA	Horizon 2020 funded project	Aims at improving the engagement of citizens by making them able to socially interact over open data, by forming or joining existing online communities that share common interest and discuss common issues.	http://routetopa.eu/

Table 16 : Invitation sent to similar EU funded projects